

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

The mining town of Cracow, Queensland: Medicine and the Public Hospital 1931-1956

Peter Stride *

University of Queensland School of Medicine, Australia.

GSC Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 14(03), 064–102

Publication history: Received on 08 January 2023; revised on 18 February 2023; accepted on 21 February 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gscarr.2023.14.3.0066>

Abstract

Cracow, Queensland, as opposed to the ancient city of Krakow in Poland, is a small town in central Queensland, Australia, notable between the 1930s and 1970s as a busy gold mining town. The clinical load of the hospital and details of the doctors who attended that facility between those dates are researched and analysed. Comparisons are made with other mining towns in Australia of previous decades, and specifically of the mine safety systems and compensation payments for miners to ascertain whether improvements had been made since the early days of mining in Australia in the 1880s.

Keywords: Cracow; Hospital; Mining; Safety systems; Accidents

1. Introduction

Between 1930 and 1970 medicine had developed into a more scientific speciality recognisable to recent medical graduates in comparison with the late nineteenth century clinical practice when most mines in Australia commenced excavating. The case load of Cracow Hospital and the treatments by the resident doctors is researched and contrasted with the medicine in hospitals of earlier Australian mines.

Trove digital newspapers are the predominant source of information. Research terms utilised were Queensland digitised newspapers 1932-1955 utilising the term, 'phrase - Cracow Hospital' and 'all these words or some of these words - mining, accident, Cracow, dr, inquiry, compensation'.

Clearly these are not peer reviewed journals but a more reliable source of information than current social media sites such as Facebook or WeChat.

2. Cracow

The current township of Cracow, Queensland, Australia, as opposed to the ancient city of Krakow in Poland, is located 494 kms North-West of Brisbane and 270 kms South-West of Rockhampton. Originally it was the home of the Wulli Wulli Australian Indigenous people probably dating back to their first settler colonisation of Australia tens of thousands of years earlier.

It first appears in the Queensland press in the 1840s with mentions of Cracow Creek, a tributary of the Dawson River, itself a major tributary of the Fitzroy River which flows out to sea through the city of Rockhampton. It is said to have been named in 1851 by the pastoralist, John Ross in reverence to the Polish who had fought valiantly for their independence. For the next four decades it was only a homestead on a cattle station, a stop on the internal mail run out of Rockhampton.

* Corresponding author: Peter Stride

Gold was first found in the Cracow district in 1875, by itinerant fossickers and a further discovery of a nugget was made by an Aboriginal stockman, Johnny Nipps in 1916. However commercial quantities of gold were not mined until 1931 when the Golden Plateau mine was established, operating continuously until 1976. In 1932, the Cracow Goldfield was proclaimed and gold production from underground and open pit operations proceeded intermittently in other local mines until 1992. A total of 850,000 ounces of gold was produced from the Cracow Goldfields with a value today of approximately two billion Australian Dollars.

Figure 1 Map of Cracow, Queensland, Australia

By 1940, Cracow was the Banana Shire's largest town, with a hospital, courthouse, school, ambulance service, shops and public buildings. The town included five cafes, barber shop, billiard saloon, two butchers, a picture theatre and a soft drink factory. The Cracow Post Office opened on 1 October 1932 and the Cracow State School opened on 12 June 1933.

Figure 2 Central Queensland, The Banana Shire

Figure 3 The Cracow Hotel Opened 1937 and still open 2022

In the 1970s the town was running down. The Golden Plateau Mine ceased operations in the mid-1970s. In 1972 several services remained, including grocers, drapers, twelve clubs, a baker and two cinemas. The hospital continued at least for outpatients until the 1990s and is today deserted, while the State primary school, opened in 1933, closed in 1997. The Post Office was destroyed in a fire in 2006.

The population which peaked in 1933 has been declining ever since. The town however, received something of a boost in 2003, with the reopening of the gold mine initially by Newcrest Mining Ltd., then subsequently and currently operated by Aeris Resources.

Table 1 Population figures

Census date	Population
1933	858
1954	367
1971	302
2006	123
2011	196
2016	89

Today the shire has devised an historic walk of Cracow, past the hall, the hotel, the Anzac memorial, the old school and the remaining shops.

3. The Doctors of Cracow

Dr John Joseph Ward 1933

Dr E.E. Wilbe 1934-37

Dr. Maxwell Ramsden 1937-1941

Dr. L. Lofkovitz 1941-1942

Dr A. M. Jones 1942-1949

Dr Burke Gaffney 1949-1952

Dr E. E. Petersen 1949-1956

Dr. William Kevin Joseph Webb 1950-1952

3.1. The Cracow District Hospital, planning stage to closure, 1933-1955

The Cracow Gold Mine opened in 1933 and the town's first doctor was John Ward.

3.1.1. 1933, Dr John Joseph Ward

Dr Ward was the resident doctor in Cracow when the mine opened in 1933 with a residence and private practice in Tenth Street. ¹

In January there was a severe storm and several citizens received lightening shocks, one of whom was treated by Dr Ward. ²

Edward O'Brien was admitted following a brawl in Cracow to the Eidsvold Hospital unconscious where Dr Hooper stated that his condition was serious, but he hoped for a recovery. Dr Ward was not mentioned. ³

In February Ward appeared as an expert witness in the Supreme Court before Justice Brennan in the trial of Herbert Chapman Roberts accused of assaulting Hilton Harold Myers.

Ward gave evidence of attending Myles shortly after the fight. He detected a fracture of the jaw, contusions on the cheek with a contused eye and he suspected another fracture. He gave Myers first aid treatment and ordered his removal to the Mt. Morgan Hospital. Myers subsequently died of his injuries, but Roberts was found not guilty as there was clear evidence from witnesses that Myers started the fight and Roberts was defending himself. ⁴

Dr Ward as Government resident doctor performed an autopsy on the body of Harry Poulton, a forty-year-old married man with two children found on the Taroom road half a mile from Cracow. Ward certified that death was due to strychnine poisoning, apparently self-administered. ⁵

By July Ward had relocated to Balonne thus there was no local doctor to treat Marie Scott who was riding her pony from her home three miles from town to school when she fell off her pony and fractured her forearm. Marie was sent seventy miles away to Eidsvold for attention. Patients were then obliged for over a year to travel to Eidsvold seventy miles away on a bush track of mediocre quality. ⁶

In 1933, a town hospital committee was formed, a temporary building was erected for inspection by the Works Department, and applications were to be called for the services of a doctor. The position had an advertised salary of £600 per annum but without living quarters. Duties were to supervise the Field Hospital and to attend members of the Industrial Groups and certain of their dependants free of charge. The right to private practice was permitted. ^{7,8}

At the end of 1933, the Government announced it would subsidise contributions donated to fund the construction of a hospital and would send an inspector from the Works Department to assist in the proposed building project. ⁹

3.1.2. 1934; Dr E.E. Wilbe

Dr E.E. Wilbe was the next resident doctor arriving in Cracow in August 1934. He first appears as a doctor in the Queensland Press in Duchess in North Queensland in 1916 and arrived in the Banana shire in 1929. ^{10,11}

The Hospital Committee spent the next two years fund raising with a multitude of social events, assessing the credential of medical applicants and considering alternative sites for a new hospital including utilising the existing Goldfield Stores Building. ¹²

Wilbe attended Vera Maud Marsten with a bullet wound in the head with powder marks round the edge of the wound indicating the shooter's proximity. She had been struck in the right temple with a 0.32 revolver bullet fired by her husband, James Marsten, in the belief that she was having an affair. Wilbe referred her on to Dr Hooper of Eidsvold who sent her to

Gayndah Hospital for an X-Ray, and on her return to Eidsvold he operated and extracted the bullet. ^{13,14,15}

Wilbe applied for a mining lease when Wolfram was discovered in the area in 1934. ¹⁶

Wilbe attended Geoffrey Olds, aged eighteen, who had partially severed the small toe of his left foot whilst working at Fairyland Station. Wilbe referred him on to Eidsvold for a formal amputation. Larry Malone, an old-age pensioner, also attended Wilbe with a rash on his head and neck from skin contact with vermin killer and was also sent to Eidsvold for further treatment.

The same issue records two other accidents requiring Wilbe's attention. Harry Mills, aged twenty-seven, jammed his hand against one of the posts in a tunnel while trucking at the Golden Plateau mine causing lacerations and Thomas Titmus, a timber getter, sustained an accidental incised wound on his left shin. ^{17,18}

William Frederick Forrest, a seventy-four-year-old was suddenly taken ill in Cracow ¹⁹ with heart failure and referred to Eidsvold where he died. The involvement of Wilbe is not stated.

3.1.3. 1935

Wilbe attended John L. McGrath, a thirty-two-year-old married man, with a fractured tibia and fibula. He was driving a truck laden with timber for Bridgman's sawmills and drove into a tree when he apparently had some reason to look backwards. The timber shot forward, striking him in the back pinning him to the steering wheel, and knocking him unconscious for a while. On coming to he found he could not extricate himself, so kept sounding the horn of his motor, ultimately attracting attention. ^{20,21}

The Banana shire council resolved to appoint Dr. Wilbe as the medical officer at Cracow six years after first appointing him to the Banana shire and six months after he commenced practice in Cracow! ²²

Dr Wilbe attended Mrs Emily Bird, an elderly lady, with a broken leg. While working in the kitchen at the residence of her son, Mr. Ralph Dean, she slipped and fell whilst trying to avoid stepping on a kitten. Today clearly recognisable as a minimal trauma fracture indicative of osteoporosis. ²³

Dr Harbison was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a gunshot injury. He was in a vehicle after going kangaroo shooting when a loaded rifle in the back of the vehicle fired spontaneously and shot him in the back through the back of the seat. He failed to respond initially to treatment, presumably by Dr Wilbe and was flown to Brisbane for specialist treatment. ²⁴

Wilbe attended Mr D Clarke, a single man employed in the mines with a deep accidental laceration in his foot. Influenza was prevalent in Cracow, but the Bulletin expected that the epidemic would be only temporary as it considered Cracow to be a very healthy place with a delightful climate, being about a thousand feet above sea level.²⁵

Mr W D Ivey, the Union Organiser, successfully claimed twenty-two shillings of unpaid wages on behalf of Mr A. Little from Dr. Wilbe under the Wages Act.²⁶

3.1.4. 1936

In 1936, the Home Secretary's department released plans for a new hospital in Cracow comprising a general ward block with male and female wards, a lavatory block, kitchen block and maids' quarters, administration offices and outbuildings included a morgue, laundry, fuel store and garage. The wooden construction with an iron roof fitted with electric light and power throughout and a septic system had an estimated cost of £ 6,700. The Department of Public Works has been requested to proceed with the work as early as possible.^{27,28}

Russell Sam, a seventeen-year-old single man working at Cracow Station was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having cut his foot with an axe while chopping firewood. Dr E.E. Wilbe inserted two stitches.²⁹

Interestingly from a historical perspective, construction of the Cracow Hospital was to occur at the same time as the construction of the new and still current University of Queensland Medical School on Herston Road behind the Children's Hospital. The school ground floor would be devoted to common rooms, workshops, operative surgery and surgical academy, and lecture room. On the first floor there was to be a commodious library fifty feet by forty-one feet, pathological laboratory, a series of lecture, room, photographic rooms and immunisation room.

The third floor was to contain a lecture room forty-one feet by fifty feet equipped with a screen for illustrated lectures and a fire-proof projection box. One wing, seventy-two feet by thirty-five feet, would house a museum; and on the other side of the lecture room there was to be a laboratory for the professors and three research laboratories,

By this time the cost of the Cracow Hospital, now to include a four bed maternity ward, had blown out to £9,152.³⁰

3.1.5. 1937

Mrs. Hovelroud was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a bullet wound in her chest. She was hurrying down the back stairs of her home with a loaded rifle in her hand to shoot a death adder when she lost her balance and fell on the weapon which discharged. The bullet narrowly missed her left lung, and after striking a rib, became lodged close behind her heart. Dr. Wilbe, who attended her, advised transportation to Brisbane for an immediate operation by a thoracic surgeon.

The patient was accompanied by her husband and two-year-old child, and Mrs. Wilbe, wife of the doctor to the General Hospital where a chest X-Ray was planned.³¹

Dr Garguilo, the medical officer at Baralaba visited Cracow to immunise children.³²

Wilbe attended Jackson Smythe, a twenty-three-year-old single man with a fractured femur.

When working as a shoveler at Golden Plateau Mine a large stone fell on him. He was transferred by air ambulance to Mundubbera Hospital and Wilbe expressly requested the pilot, Mr. A. Gilbertson, to exercise extreme care landing the plane so that the injured leg was not jarred. Scarcely necessary advice for a pilot!³³

Nearly a year elapsed with no progress before it was announced that the successful tender for the hospital construction was made by Mr H. Kaiser and that work was starting with a probable construction time of sixteen weeks.³⁴

Dr Hyndes was offered the appointment of medical officer in Cracow but declined and fresh applications were invited for the position.³⁵

3.1.6. Dr Maxwell Ramsden

Mr. Walter Hardie was injured at the Golden Plateau Mine suffering a severe scalp wound, and serious lacerations of his right ear and right arm. Hardie was employed as chuteman pulling mullock from the chute, when the mullock, loosened by the recent heavy rains, freed itself and shot out over the board at the mouth of the chute. Mr. Hardie was hit on the

forehead and somersaulted over a rope backwards forty feet down a mullock pass on to the 240ft level. Prior to the opening of Cracow Hospital, he was conveyed to the Mundubbera Hospital.

Dr. Ramsden, of Goondiwindi accepted the appointment as medical officer to the Cracow Hospital. ³⁶

Cracow District Hospital, opening and closure, 1938-1955

As the Cracow Hospital neared completion, Matron Davis accepted the position of matron and Dr. Maxwell Ramsden, of Goondiwindi, arrived to commence his duties as Medical Officer to the Cracow Hospital. ³⁷

3.1.7. 1938

Dr. M. Ramsden attended Roy Lane, a married man, with a severe scalp wound, abrasions to the body and a fractured clavicle following a bicycle accident when he skidded on the Theodore-Cracow Road. ³⁸

The Cracow Hospital finally opened in March with the successful delivery of a baby the following day with mother and child as the first recorded inpatients. ³⁹

Dr. Ramsden reported that there were five inpatients remaining on March 31st after the first week in the new hospital. During April there were twenty-one admissions with six remaining in hospital on April 30th. Eighty-six patients had visited outpatients for a total of one hundred and eighty consultations. Curiously, the paper reported that five general anaesthetics, and three local anaesthetics had been administered yet only one operation had been performed! No deaths were reported. ⁴⁰

Although the hospital had been open and functioning for the citizens of Cracow for a month with a full component of expert professionals busy working, an official bureaucratic opening ceremony for administrators was performed by the Minister for Health and Home Affairs, Mr. B. M. Hanlon. ⁴⁵

The first named identifiable inpatient in Cracow Hospital was Mr B. F. Clarke who sustained injuries to the clavicle from an accident when felling scrub. ⁴⁶

Dr. Ramsden reported to the Hospital Board that during August there were four births, ten admissions, two hundred and ten outpatient consultations and nine operations, two major and seven minor. He noted that a case of diphtheria from Theodore was amongst the admissions. There is no press record of twins being born in Cracow in August as reported in one town history in Facebook. ⁴⁷

Diphtheria was once among the top-ten causes of child death, with more than 4,000 deaths from diphtheria in Australia between 1926 and 1935. Cases fell dramatically following the introduction of vaccines in the late 1930s. There were no cases of respiratory diphtheria in children in Australia between 1992 and 2022. However over the same period, there were seven cases of respiratory diphtheria in adults, two of whom died, both predictably unvaccinated.

Dr. Ramsden reported to the December Hospital Board meeting that during the previous month there were seven admissions, three discharges, six deliveries with one death and one premature baby. Ninety-two outpatients were seen for a total of one hundred and eighty four consultations. Seventeen operations were performed, five major and twelve minor, plus ten dental extractions. ⁴⁸

3.1.8. 1939

At the December general meeting of the Cracow Hospital committee it was proposed that a doctor's residence be built on a site adjacent to the hospital. Dr. M. M. Ramsden applied for one month's leave in March which was granted.

Wilbe is last reported in the Cracow area when his Wolfram claim is mentioned. ⁴⁹

Dr. Ramsden reported that there were four remaining inpatients at the end of October, four male and one female. There were twelve admissions during November, eight male and four female, followed by thirteen discharges, nine male and four female leaving four remaining inpatients, three male and one female with no deaths. (the figures do not add up, a recurring error in the monthly reports.)

In the Obstetric Ward there were four remaining in hospital at end of October, two were admitted during month, and five were discharged during November leaving one remaining in hospital at the end of November. Two babies were born and sixteen operations performed during the month.

Ninety-six outpatients were seen during the month, sixty-five males and thirty-one females, for a total of one hundred and seventeen consultations, eighty-nine male and twenty-eight female. One case of scarlet fever was admitted during the month.⁵⁰

George Kenniff, aged sixty-three, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having sustained abrasions and shock when attacked by a fortunately dehorned bull at his farm at Theodore.

Dr. Ramsden recommended the purchase of an iron lung at a cost of £40/10/0, not only for cases of infantile paralysis but as a potentially life-saving device for other causes of respiratory failure.⁵¹

4. Iron Lungs

The use of iron lungs is largely obsolete in modern medicine in favour of positive-pressure invasive or non-invasive forms of ventilation and thanks to vaccines eradicating polio and tetanus in most of the world. However, in 2020, the COVID-19 pandemic revived some interest in the device as a cheap, readily-producible substitute for positive-pressure ventilators should demand exceed supply.

An iron lung is a type of negative pressure ventilator (NPV), a mechanical respirator which encloses most of a person's body, and varies the air pressure in the enclosed space, to assist breathing when muscle control is lost. Previously it was used for diseases including polio and botulism and certain poisons, e.g. barbiturates or tubocurarine.

The concept of a body container for ventilation is several hundred years old. In 1918 Dr Stueart of South Africa designed an airtight wooden box sealed at the waist and shoulders with clay and powered by motor-driven bellows specifically for the treatment of polio.

Drinker and Shaw tank in USA in 1928 developed commercial quantities of the Drinker Iron Lung for treatment of polio.

Figure 5 Drinker Iron Lung

An Australian, June Middleton of Melbourne, holds the World Record, as the person who spent the longest time in an iron lung according to the *Guinness Book of Records* having spent more than 60 years in her iron lung up to her death on October 30, 2009 aged 83.

Dr. Ramsden reported statistics for December to the monthly hospital committee. There were three remaining inpatients at the end of November followed by eighteen admissions, seventeen discharges, but no deaths leaving three remaining inpatients. (again the figures do not add up).

In the obstetric ward there was one remaining patient at the end of the previous month ward, followed by three admissions, two discharges and one birth leaving one remaining inpatient. (a patient appears to have vanished from each ward!)

Ninety-eight outpatients attended for ninety-nine consultations. Twelve general and eight local anaesthetics were administered yet only four operations were performed!

A leakage in the septic system was noted by the Shire Health Inspector necessitating a full plumbing review, and Messrs Brown and Broad architectural design for the proposed residence for the doctor was selected.⁵²

Mr W. Hibbins was admitted to the Cracow Hospital under Dr. Ramsden suffering from a severely lacerated forehead sustained when the vehicle in which he was travelling crashed into a tree at Doctor's Gully, about eight miles from Theodore township. The car driven by Mr W. Hutchison, of Woolton station crashed when the accelerator jammed.

W. Hutchinson, received lacerations to the face, arms, and chest while Mr S. Hutchinson, the other passenger suffered lacerations on the leg. These two were treated at Cracow Hospital and discharged.

Mr E. Bowmon, of Theodore, was also admitted to the Cracow Hospital for a few days under Dr. Ramsden suffering from injuries to his hand received when engaged in shaping a spike from a piece of wood. The axe slipped and badly cut the thumb and forefinger.

The recent purchase of the new ambulance car enabled faster and more comfortable travel in the district.⁵³

Dr. Ramsden reported statistics for February to the monthly hospital committee. There were twenty-three admissions, eleven males and twelve female, and twenty-two discharges, twelve male and ten female leaving five remaining inpatients on January 31st, two male and three female. The daily inpatient average was 1.9 males and 3.4 females. No deaths were recorded.

There were two admissions, two births and two discharges in the Obstetric ward, leaving two mothers and two infants remaining in hospital on January 31st for a daily average of 1.7 mothers and 0.7 infants.

One hundred and twenty-five outpatients, sixty-six male and fifty-nine female attended for one hundred and thirty-four consultations. The daily average number of outpatients was 6.3 males and 3.0 females. Three major and fourteen minor operations were performed and there were ten dental extractions.

It is a measure of the town demographics and the advent of married adults that female patients in Cracow Hospital outnumbered males for the first time.⁵⁴

Dr Ramsden applied for a month's leave in March.⁵⁵

Theodore J. Featheringham was admitted with a severe incision to his right leg received when his axe glanced off the tree on which he was working whilst ringbarking on Mr S. Becker's property.⁵⁶

Mr. James Sinclair, aged sixty-two, a returned soldier and current prospector died in the Cracow Hospital. His diagnosis and cause of death were not stated.⁵⁷

Dr. Ramsden reported that during April sixteen patients were admitted to the general wards and two pregnant ladies to the obstetric ward. There was one birth, no deaths and one hundred and seventy-three consultations in the outpatients department. Dr. Ramsden application for five weeks' leave of absence was granted.⁵⁸

Ten babies were born in one week in the Cracow Hospital, a record figure for a single week to date.⁵⁹

Dr. W. S. Page was acting as locum tenens while Dr. Ramsden was on holidays.⁶⁰

David Robinson was admitted to the Cracow Hospital under Dr. Ramsden semi-conscious suffering from a fracture of the base of the skull. He was working in the Roses Pride Goldmine operating a horse-driven windlass which hauled skips of ore to the surface.

The harness broke and the windlass flew back, striking Robinson on the head. He was dangerously ill overnight and flown to Brisbane the next day for specialist treatment.

Many newspaper reports noted with equal importance that 3001b. of gold, valued at £30,000 was on the same flight. Four months later an inquest into Robinson's injuries was held in the Cracow Court House. Warden A. Murray presided,

and the Mines Department was represented by Mr. O. Carlson. The finding was that the occurrence was accidental and no blame was attachable to anyone. ^{61,62,62,64,65}

Dr. Ramsden reported that during May, there were eleven admissions, fifteen discharges and two deaths. In the obstetric ward there were eleven admissions and ten deliveries. Two hundred and twenty patients were treated in the outpatients' department. A request from the Matron for extra remuneration for extra work done by the nursing staff was refused. Little changes as the decades go by! ⁶⁶

A mining inquiry was held at the Cracow Court House before Mr Warden Murray, of Maryborough, and a board of Cracow mining assessors to investigate the circumstances of a nearly fatal burning accident at the Golden Plateau Mine to Cecil Davison.

Evidence was given by Davison and Stanley Lacey, who was near Davison when the accident occurred. Davison was charging a hole with powder and had actually finished the job and had lit the fuse when some powder which he had spilt on the ground around the hole, caught fire from the burning fuse and exploded, setting fire to Davison's clothing and burning him severely about the face and body. He was in the local hospital for a long period and, for a time, his condition was considered serious.

The evidence presented was deemed to simply prove that the accident could not have been foreseen, and the word compensation is not to be seen. ⁶⁷

Dr. Ramsden reported to the monthly meeting of the Cracow Hospital Committee that during July there had been five births and one hundred and thirty-one outpatients had been treated. ⁶⁸

World War II commenced with England and France declaring war on Germany following the Nazi invasion of Poland, and the bombing of Krakow amongst other Polish cities. ^{69,70}

Mr William Chrono White, the seventy-eight-year old owner of the station property, Southend near Theodore, died in the Cracow Hospital after only a few days' illness, leaving a widow and nine children. The cause of his death is not published. ⁷¹

Dr. Ramsden reported to the monthly meeting of the Cracow Hospital Committee that during August thirteen people were admitted to the general ward, seven to the obstetric ward and that a hundred and seventeen were treated at the outpatients' department. ⁷²

Leon Hart was admitted to the Cracow Hospital under Dr. Ramsden suffering from exhaustion and probably dehydration and exposure. He left his camp in Cracow on Monday morning and was found lost in the bush on Tuesday afternoon. A search party found him party a mile and a half off :the Cracow main, road and two and a half miles from the township.

There is a considerable mortality being lost in the Queensland bush under a merciless summer sun with temperature around thirty degrees and little water or shade. ⁷³

Dr. Ramsden reported to the Cracow Hospital Committee monthly meeting that during October twenty patients were admitted to the general ward and seventeen discharged.

Ninety-eight outpatients received a total of one hundred and fifty consultations. ⁷⁴

Dr. Ramsden appeared as an expert witness at the Coroner's inquest into the death of Benjamin Kent, aged thirty-two, who collapsed and died suddenly on October 23rd, 1938. Ramsden's post-mortem revealed coronary occlusion and toxic myocarditis. The coroner was satisfied that death was from natural causes. Heart failure from coronary artery diseases would not be unusual, but inflammatory or infectious myocarditis would not necessarily be associated with coronary occlusion in a young man. ⁷⁵

Dr Wilbe is last reported in the Cracow area when his Wolfram claim is mentioned. ⁷⁶

Mrs Myra Millicent Patterson, wife of Mr Benjamin Patterson, died in Cracow Hospital under the care of Dr Ramsden at the age of thirty-one. No diagnosis is given, but she left a two day old son, strongly suggesting some post-natal disease such as haemorrhage, sepsis, thromboembolic disease or depression.

Between 1930 and 1970, maternal mortality in Australia fell from 0.6% to 0.01% but was still 0.45% in 1940. ^{77,78}

4.1.1. 1940

Dr. M. W. Ramsden, of Cracow, appeared as an expert witness in the Police Court where Edward Roy Weldon, a labourer, was charged with the wilful murder of Alice Catherine Dyer at Theodore on December 19th 1939.

Ramsden said that he conducted a post-mortem examination on Alice Dyer finding bruises on her neck could have been caused by thumbs or fingers, and a line of bruising could have been caused by a piece of cloth, such as the piece exhibited, tied tightly round the neck. The bruising on the side of the windpipe would have been quite sufficient to cause death. An abrasion on the nose and upper lip and the bleeding from the nose could have been caused by a blow from a fist. Alice Dyer was not pregnant and no spermatozoa were found on a vaginal swab.

Weldon admitted to murdering Alice, they had been walking together when she refused to see him again in favour of another man. A fight commenced in which he pushed her over and strangled her. Weldon was committed for trial at the Rockhampton Criminal Sittings the following month where he was subsequently found guilty and sentenced to life imprisonment with hard labour. ^{79,80}

Mr J. B. Haupt was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with accidental trauma to his knee and ankle sustained at the Golden Plateau mine when he slipped down a ladder.

Peter Michael Gavin, aged fifty, died in the Cracow Hospital of an unstated condition. He had worked on different stations in the area for a dozen years. ⁸¹

Dr. Hill reported to the Cracow Hospital Committee monthly meeting that the daily average of patients in January was fifteen. It is not specified if this refers to inpatients or outpatients though the latter is more likely. Dr Hill was presumably a locum for Dr Ramsden. ⁸²

Max Alfred Friers, a Swiss native watchmaker, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having disappeared from the township and been found lost at a mining battery five miles away by a search party that had been looking for him from the time he was reported missing early that day. However Friers disappeared unnoticed again from hospital about one o'clock the following morning and for the second time within a week police and a black tracker went searching for him. Nearly two weeks later he had still not been found in spite of large parties of men on foot and horseback searching for him. Unfortunately, the heavy rain had erased all traces of footprints.

He was finally located on 14th September at Pendale station, fifty miles from Chinchilla. Except for three meals at outback houses he had lived on boiled and raw prickly pear fruit. He was surprisingly in a fairly good physical condition when found by a police search party.

Presumably, he had some cognitive decline. ^{83,84,85,86}

Reg Sauer, aged ten was admitted unconscious to the Cracow Hospital suffering from wounds and abrasions to his back, hips, and nose. He had been thrown from a horse on his father's farm and was dragged some distance. The accident was not witnessed.

Matron Cunningham hosted a farewell evening supper for the Cracow Hospital Committee secretary, Mr Walter William. There were card games, speeches and a presentation.

Dr Ramsden said that Williams had been a tremendous help in furthering the good of the hospital. ⁸⁷

The residence for the medical officer of the Cracow Hospital was reported to be part of the very brisk building activity in Cracow. ⁸⁸

Douglas McLeod was admitted to the Cracow Hospital, suffering from severe scalds when he fell into a tub of hot water prepared for his bath. The infant son of Mr and Mrs D. McLeod, he was reported to be progressing favourably. ⁸⁹

Dr. Ramsden reported to the Cracow Hospital Committee monthly meeting that the daily average number of inpatients at the hospital during May was 1.6 in the general ward, and 3.7 in the Obstetric Ward. One hundred and two outpatients were seen for a total of two hundred and forty-five consultations, an average of eight daily. ⁹⁰

Matthew James O'Shea was admitted to the Cracow Hospital unconscious with severe lacerations to the head received whilst felling scrub at Gibihi, Moura. Kevin Carmody, the fourteen year-old son of Mr and Mrs Syd, Carmody, Clare station was also admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a broken leg sustained when thrown against a tree while out riding. ⁹¹

Two brother, George and Edward Bridgeman, were admitted to the Cracow Hospital with either broken legs or dislocated hips sustained in a motor vehicle accident fourteen miles from Cracow. They and their brother Frank, all timber cutters were hauling timber in a lorry when it skidded in mud, hit a tree and overturned. Frank was pinned, to the ground by a log fifty inches in circumference which rolled on to his neck.

Edward, although suffering intense pain from his broken leg, crawled to the lorry, dragged an eighty pound jack to where his brother Frank was lying on the ground and raised the log off him. Frank now was the only one who could walk, set out for help. After walking for a mile he was picked up by Mr J. Gibson, who took him thirteen miles into the Cracow Hospital. There he informed the doctor and ambulance who set out immediately to retrieve the other two brothers who had then been three hours out in the rain. Frank, who was not seriously injured thanks to Edward was treated for bruises and shock in the Cracow Hospital then discharged. ^{92,93}

Mr H. M. Rickards was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from bums to his leg sustained whilst burning off undergrowth at his son's station, Fairyland.

Leslie Cockerill, age seventeen, was also admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering an injury to his shoulder when knocked by a horse while working at Camboon Station. He was reported to be progressing favourably. ⁹⁴

Mr Tom Lawless, a mechanic, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital, suffering from shock and a lacerated hand sustained in the second of two consecutive motor vehicle accidents within an hour. Initially he was driving to the weir on the Dawson River with his wife, baby, and two friends when a wheel came off. No-one was hurt, and as they were only a short distance from the town he decided to return and get another vehicle.

He was returning with another utility on the Cracow-Theodore Road when the steering column became disconnected and the truck overturned, pinning his hand underneath the broken frame of the hood. Fortunately the second accident occurred close to where his party was waiting for him, and they were able to release him to be conveyed by ambulance to the hospital. ^{95,96}

Dr. Alexander, of Gayndah relieved Dr. M. W. Ramsden as Medical Officer in Cracow while Ramsden was on holidays in Southport. ⁹⁷

Jack Jordan, machine man on the Golden Plateau, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a severe injury to the thumb of his left hand when the drill which he was operating broke and crushed the thumb. ⁹⁸

Jill Coates was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from severe scalds caused by falling into a bucket of hot water at the residence of her grandmother, Gyranda. The two and a half year old daughter of Mr and Mrs John Coates of Rockhampton, she was reported to be progressing favourably. ⁹⁹

Mr. Joe Haupt was admitted to the Cracow Hospital for the second time in ten months with another accident at the Golden Plateau Mine. On this occasion he suffered injuries to his right arm which was broken in at least three places when his arm became entangled in a rope when lowering timber with a winch. He was sent on to Mundubbera for X-ray in the absence of an X-ray machine in Cracow. On neither occasion was there any inquiry into the cause of the accidents or mention of paid sick leave or compensation. ¹⁰⁰

4.1.2. 1941

Dr M. Ramsden was reappointed to the Cracow Hospital committee. John Sloss, an elderly man from Camboon, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having sustained injuries to his knee when he was kicked by a cow but was progressing favourably.

Matron Cunningham had returned from six weeks' holiday spent in Melbourne and Sydney. Sister Hese, who had been relieving Matron Cunningham, had returned to Brisbane. ¹⁰¹

Mr W. J. Morris, aged twenty-eight was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from concussion, abrasions to the right eye, and shock. Morris was mustering cattle for Mr F. Horn at the time when his horse shied and threw him heavily to the ground, where he lay for an hour and a half before being found. He was reported to be progressing favourably.

Jean Latchford, the twelve year old daughter of Mr and Mrs C. Latchford of Theodore, was treated at the Cracow Hospital, but not detained, having sustained severe lacerations to the thigh when she fell over. Many adults had been treated in hospital recently suffering from the local epidemic of measles. ¹⁰²

The Health Inspector planned an immunisation campaign against diphtheria and whooping cough in Cracow. ¹⁰³

The Medical Officer, either Dr Ramsden or Dr. L. Lofkovitz submitted the report for February to the monthly meeting of the Cracow Hospital Board. There had been twenty-six admissions, twenty male and six female, twenty-three discharges, sixteen male and seven female, leaving eight remaining inpatients, six male and two female.

The daily average number of inpatients was 5.1, males 4.1, females 1.0.

There were two admissions to the obstetric ward followed by three discharges leaving one remaining inpatient. The daily average of mothers was 1.4, infants 0.83, total 2.23. There had been three births.

One hundred and nineteen outpatients, fifty-four male and sixty-five female were attended for a total of one hundred and sixty-seven consultations, seventy-six male and ninety-one female, a daily average of male 2.3, female 3.2. total 5.5. ¹⁰⁴

Dr and Mrs. Maxwell Ramsden and their two small children moved to Longreach after being medical officer at Cracow for more than three years. Ramsden was farewelled in the Cracow Hall, and eulogistic references were made to his services to the district. ^{105,106}

4.1.3. Dr. L. Lofkovitz

Dr. L. Lofkovitz was appointed medical officer to the Cracow Hospital as replacement for Dr M. Ramsden. Mr. Justus Angwin, aged sixty-seven died unexpectedly in Cracow where he was being treated for pleurisy for four days apparently successfully before he died suddenly with a heart attack. It does not specify whether he was being treated in the hospital. One wonders if the initial diagnosis of pleurisy mistook that for angina. He had worked most of his life in mines including the Ivanhoe Gold Mine in Boulder, Western Australia and the Golden Plateau Mine in Cracow. ¹⁰⁷

Cliff Farrall was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a broken leg caused when the horse he was riding fell. He was reported to be improving rapidly. ¹⁰⁸

Charles Lambert was treated at the Cracow Hospital for facial injuries caused when a fuse prematurely exploded in the mine which he is prospecting, then allowed to return home. His son-in-law, M. Breingan, was slightly injured by pebbles from the explosion, but not admitted.

George Harold Rodwell, aged fifty-two died in the Cracow Hospital of unstated disease. Mr Rodwell had been a farmer in the Theodore district for three years and was a returned soldier, he was buried with military honours. ¹⁰⁹

Dr Lofkovitz of Cracow, was appointed medical officer of health for No. 1 District. ¹¹⁰

Edward McNamee, a twenty-seven year old jockey, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital ¹¹¹ suffering from severe head and face injuries owing to his horse falling at the Theodore Races.

4.1.4. 1942

The Medical Officer's report at the February meeting of the Cracow Hospital Committee stated that there were three patients remaining at the end of the previous month, followed by nineteen admissions, twelve discharges, and one death leaving nine remaining inpatients.

In the obstetric ward there were two admissions and five discharges leaving the ward empty. Two hundred and twenty outpatients were seen for a total of three hundred and sixty-one consultations. ¹¹²

The Ambulance Superintendent's reported that for the month of February there were four accidents, one hundred and twenty-two transports, and twenty-three office cases for a total of one hundred and twenty-nine cases. The vehicle travelled three hundred and twenty-two miles including two trips on the Theodore Road for fifty-two miles, and two trips to Camboon Station for one hundred and twenty miles. ¹¹³

Dr. L. Lofkovitz reported that for the month of February, there were nineteen admissions, seventeen discharges and one death leaving seven inpatients for a daily average of 9.43. In the Obstetric Ward there were two admissions and one discharge leaving one inpatient.

One hundred and eighty-nine outpatients attended for a total of three hundred and one consultations. ¹¹⁴

The Department of Public Health officially approved of the appointment of Drs W. Cohn and L. Lofkovitz as Medical Officers of Health to the council. ¹¹⁵

Dr. L. Lofkovitz, Matron Gunthorpe and the hospital secretary all resigned within a week. There does not appear to have been any specific controversial issue or administrative incompetence precipitating these events.

Dr. L. Lofkovitz reported that for the month of May there had been three hundred and seventy nine outpatients attending for a total of six hundred and thirty-one consultations, for a daily average of 20.56. There were six remaining inpatients at the end of the month followed by twenty-five admissions, twenty discharges and one death leaving eight remaining inpatients for a daily average of 7.34. There were four admissions and discharges from the obstetric ward for a daily average of 2.6, leaving the unit empty again at the end of May. ¹¹⁶

The resignation of Dr Lofkovitz had been accepted at a special hospital council meeting the previous week. ¹¹⁷

The Cracow Hospital advised that it had no accommodation for the isolation and treatment of infectious disease cases. A probable administrative oversight in view of the periodic potentially severe infectious diseases seen in Cracow. ¹¹⁸

4.1.5. Dr Alice Muriel Jones

Dr Jones was appointed Medical Officer of Health for No. 1 division of the shire including Cracow. ¹¹⁹

Mr F. Heiniger of Cracow claimed maintenance in respect of himself and his family while they were isolated at his home during the period one of his children was suffering from diphtheria. It was decided to advise that as the case had occurred more than thirteen months ago the claim could not be considered.

Frederick Walsh, a forty-eight-year-old married man was killed instantly when a lorry overturned at the Golden Plateau Gold Mine in Cracow. Walsh, a returned soldier of the last war, had worked with the company for eight years. His death was the first recorded fatality at the mine. No coronial inquiry was recorded in the press. ¹²⁰

4.1.6. 1943

Mrs Reg Garcia died in Cracow unexpectedly one day after the birth of twin daughters. The Herald does not state whether this was at home or in hospital though the Obstetric Ward would seem the most likely venue. The cause of death is also not stated but postnatal problems would be probable. She is survived by her husband, two small sons and the twin daughters.

Ambulance data for the previous three months were attendance at sixty accidents, routine transport for a hundred and forty-nine cases and seventy-six patients seen in the office.

Mileage totalled three hundred and sixty-six. No details are given of the number conveyed to Cracow Hospital. ^{121,122}

Mr J. Olds was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from an injury to his eye having been struck in the eye with a stick at Rocky Bar, a property west of Eidsvold. He was transferred to Rockhampton for specialist treatment.

Lennie Bams, the twelve months' old son of Mr and Mrs A. Bams, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from the effects of drinking kerosene but was progressing favourably.

The World War continued with two sons of Cracow in print, Pte John Cowle had been reported killed in action, and. Sgt J. Wilson, wireless operator air gunner had been reported missing over enemy territory. ¹²³

Mr. Mervyn Cope was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from severe bruises. He was fortunate to escape serious injury having been thrown from a horse being broken in and was dragged around the enclosure. ¹²⁴

William Edward Ritchie, aged fifty, an employee of the Golden Plateau Mine, was taken by a neighbour to the Cracow Hospital suffering severe burns where he died some hours after admission. The deceased lived by himself and is believed to have fallen into the fire at his home. ¹²⁵

Dr Burke Gaffney was appointment as medical officer of health for Nos 2 and 3 divisions of the Banana shire and able to visit Cracow occasionally. ¹²⁶

Brian White, aged fifteen was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from an injury to his knee when thrown from a horse at his home at Isla. He was found by Mr White and brought into the hospital for treatment. ¹²⁷

Mr A. H. Hunt was transferred to Brisbane for further medical attention following thirty weeks in the Cracow Hospital with an unspecified condition. ¹²⁸

4.1.7. 1944

The Cracow Hospital monthly medical report stated that one hundred and nineteen outpatients, fifty male and sixty-nine female had been seen. Seven patients, three male and four female had been admitted. Four pregnant women were admitted to the obstetric ward and four babies were delivered. ¹²⁹

Mr A. Webb was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from injuries through cutting his foot with an axe. ¹³⁰

Dr A. M. Jones had become the medical officer to Cracow Hospital. She reported that in March, ten patients, five male and five female were admitted and all discharged except one female. There were no deaths. Two women were admitted to the obstetric ward and both discharged, one after a successful delivery, leaving an empty unit.

In the outpatient department, forty-three males visited for eighty-three consultations, a daily average of 2.67. Thirty seven females attended for fifty-seven consultations, a daily average of 1.93. Dr Jones also requested leave of absence from May 26th to June 20th. ^{131,132}

Dr J. Hains visited Cracow on April 27th to perform three tonsillectomies. Hains was the equivalent of today's general practitioner not an otolaryngologist, an example of the diverse skills required in remote communities. ¹³³

Mr. Robert Archibald Hamilton died in the Cracow Hospital. His age and diagnosis were not stated, however he was the elderly station owner of Rocky Bar Station. He had not been in the best of health for some time and so his passing was not altogether unexpected. ¹³⁴

Dr A. M. Jones of Cracow, advised that she was prepared to attend to the immunisation of children against diphtheria at Theodore, but that she would be away on holidays from May 26th. ¹³⁵

Dr A. M. Jones had returned from a vacation spent in Stanthorpe and Brisbane. Dr P. E. Corliss, who had been locum tenens returned to his practice in Casino. ¹³⁶

Alan Long, the infant son of Mr and Mrs A. G. Long of Linga Longa died in the Cracow Hospital as a result of extensive burns on his left side, chest, back and arm, caused by his clothes being ignited from a fire in the kitchen store. ¹³⁷

Dr A. M. Jones, Cracow, advised that she had given the first diphtheria immunisation injection to approximately fifty children in the Theodore area and had made arrangements to give the second and final injections. ¹³⁸

The Medical Officer's monthly report showed one hundred and eight outpatients attended the clinic for one hundred and sixty-five consultations, a daily average of 5.32. There were four remaining inpatients, followed by fifteen admissions, fifteen discharges and one death leaving three remaining at end of month, for a daily average of 4.00. ¹³⁹

Mr James Patterson, senior was reported to be in the Cracow Hospital in a serious but unspecified condition. ¹⁴⁰

The Medical Officer reported that for October, one hundred and twelve outpatients were seen for a total of one hundred and fifty-eight consultations, a daily average of 5.09. ¹⁴¹

4.1.8. 1945

In the general ward, three inpatients remained at the end of the previous month, admissions were not reported but twelve had been discharged, making a daily average of 1.98 inpatients. In the obstetric ward five patients were admitted and discharged for a daily average of 1.07.

The medical officer's report showed that for January the number of patients treated in the outpatients' department was one hundred and sixty. Seventeen inpatients were admitted during the month and nineteen discharged, leaving four at the end of the month. There were no obstetric cases. ¹⁴²

The medical officer's report for February showed that one hundred and nine outpatients received two hundred and eighteen consultations. There were twelve admissions and fourteen discharges leaving three remaining inpatients. The medical officer's report showed that the daily average number of patients in February was 5.68. Four expectant mother were admitted to the obstetric ward and one discharged leaving three remaining. ^{143,144}

The Medical Officer's reported that in March one hundred and six outpatients attended for one hundred and ninety-two consultations for a daily average 6.16. Eleven patients were admitted and the same number discharged leaving three remaining at end of the month. No deaths occurred. Four mothers delivered in the obstetric ward, then seven mothers and babies were discharged leaving an empty ward. ¹⁴⁵

The Medical Officer reported that in April one hundred and thirteen outpatients attended for one hundred and forty eight consultations. There were three remaining inpatients followed by twelve admissions, twelve discharges and no deaths leaving three remaining again at end of month.

Mrs Ada Victoria Rose Maberly, wife of Mr J. W. Maberly, aged eighty-four died in the Cracow Hospital. Her cause of death was not stated but she had been an invalid, bedbound since a stroke five years previously and had deteriorated recently. ^{146, 147}

In June 1945 there was an epidemic of chicken-pox in the town, and a number of children were absent from school. No fatalities or hospital admissions were reported. ¹⁴⁸

During 1945 the administration of Cracow Hospital devolved to a combined Cracow-Eidsvold Hospital committee. Thus when this body welcomed Dr J. Hains it is not clear to which hospital he had been appointed. Regretfully from a clinician's perspective, this committee released to the press statements about hospital finances, who was appointed to the committee and who had donated cakes to the hospital, while the primary purpose of the hospital, caring for patients was largely forgotten! On one occasion the purchase of a cow for the hospital was announced while details of the clinical load and professional hospital staff was totally absent! Hospital patient data released to the press appears greatly curtailed. ^{149,150}

The medical officer reported a daily average of 6.55 patients at the Cracow Hospital for the previous month. It is not clear if there are inpatients or outpatients. ¹⁵¹

Edward James Boldery, a fifty-two year old former amateur boxing champion of Queensland of Gayndah, was fatally injured in a car accident between Cracow and Theodore. He died in the Cracow Hospital without regaining consciousness. The steering appeared to be defective, and the car turned over and then righted itself. Boldery and Mr G. McNamara, the other occupant of the car, were both thrown out. McNamara escaped with a few bruises and cuts and shock and was able to get to Woolton station to call the ambulance. ^{152,153}

4.1.9. 1946

Cracow Hospital averaged 5.33 patients daily. It is not stated whether these are inpatients or outpatients. ¹⁵⁴

The death of Doris Evelyn Hall, who died at a private hospital on January 24th 1946 was the subject of a coronial inquest under Mr R. Power, District Coroner. She had previously been an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital for several months, but no diagnosis is stated. Apparently at times she showed complete loss of body power. On several occasions she had stated that if nothing could be done she preferred to be dead.

The diagnosis from this data is uncertain, more clinical information on the nature of her 'turns' would have clarified the diagnosis. Cataplexy, hypokalaemic paralysis, epilepsy, myasthenia, thyrotoxicosis or hysteria merit consideration.

Subsequently she was admitted to a private hospital under Dr N. C. Talbot suffering from a thyrotoxic goitre For fourteen days prior to the operation she was given treatment. Lugol's iodine was the standard preoperative treatment to reduce gland vascularity and thyroxine release.

The first week she took the turns daily, but during the later stage she had only three turns in five days. Before Talbot operated he knew she was a bad risk, but he had hoped that she would regain enough health so as to have the goitre removed by an operation. Normally a local anaesthetic would have been used, but as she was subject to turns, he gave the deceased a general anaesthetic.

The operation was commenced at 9 a.m. At 10.10 a.m. it was concluded with the exception of closing the wound, when suddenly the deceased's breathing stopped. Everything possible was done to stimulate her cardiac centres. Both he and Dr Wooster, who administered the anaesthetic, worked on Mrs Hall for three-quarters of an hour. He was of the opinion that death was due to surgical shock affecting the heart, the nervous mechanism of which had been affected by deceased's illness. Her only chance of retaining her health was to have the operation.

The presence of other comorbidity is not excluded and possibly the thyroid function was not adequately controlled. A few more years saw the development of the protein bound iodine test for thyroid function but it was not available in 1946. Possibly some surgical problem caused respiratory obstruction. Unfortunately, an autopsy appears not to have been performed.

The inquest was closed and the depositions, together with the Coroner's report, were forwarded to the Department of Justice. ¹⁵⁵

Cracow Hospital had an average of 3.98 patients daily probably for February according to the matron's very limited report. ¹⁵⁶

Cracow Hospital had an average of 5.59 patients daily during March according to the very limited details of the Medical Officer's report. ¹⁵⁷

Mr N. McDonald, a drover, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering internal injuries when his horse fell on him. His condition was said to be fairly serious. The main anxiety would be the possibility of a ruptured internal organ. In 1960 a diagnostic laparotomy may have been performed and by the 1980s an abdominal ultrasound or CAT scan could have excluded some major abdominal complication. ¹⁵⁸

Eidsvold Hospital was visited by Mr Foley, the Health Minister, to inspect the establishment and discuss the possibility of erecting a new hospital in Eidsvold, an event likely to impact on the viability of Cracow Hospital, ninety kilometres distant. ¹⁵⁹

Cracow Hospital had an average of 5.68 patients daily during April. ¹⁶⁰

The Medical Officer reported that Cracow Hospital had an average of 6.42 patients daily during June. ¹⁶¹

The Medical Officer reported to the Cracow-Eidsvold Hospital committee that Cracow Hospital had an average of 4.71 patients daily during September. Dr Jones replied to a committee member inquiring about the effect of dead cattle in the river leading to the dam on the town drinking supply. She stated there was currently enough rain water in the tanks for drinking and cooking purposes. She strongly advised the public to boll the river water before use.

Dr A. Jones was subsequently holidaying in Brisbane, and during her absence Dr Arnott, of Sydney, was acting as locum tenens. ¹⁶²

Dr Alice Muriel Jones gave medical evidence to the Theodore Court of Petty Sessions at the trial of the brothers George Brown and John William Brown and Edward Joseph Cralow. They were accused of unlawfully assaulting Constable Logan Hoey and thereby occasioning him bodily harm.

Following an affray in which the three men assaulted the policeman, Sergeant Lange said he found Constable Hoey in a dazed condition in the cafe with a number of facial injuries. He was conveyed to the Cracow Hospital where, after examination by Dr Jones, he was admitted about 3.30 a.m.

His injuries included swelling and abrasions above the right eye, swelling of the upper lip and inside the bottom lip, swelling of the right side of his jaw and bruises and tenderness over the left jaw, swelling behind the ears, abrasions on the left lip. He was discharged three days later and had been suffering from severe headaches since his discharge. Many witnesses observed the fight.

The three men were committed to trial by jury at the next criminal sitting of the Supreme Court at Rockhampton, where Cralow and George Brown were both found guilty. His Honour said he would not record a conviction against Cralow but remanded the prisoner for sentence if called upon for sentence within six months. He fined George Brown £10, in default of six months' imprisonment, and discharged John William Brown. ^{163,164,165,166}

4.1.10. 1947

Miss Katie Ferguson, aged fifty-seven, died in the Cracow Hospital. She sustained a stroke and passed away soon afterwards. She had been transferred from the position of post-mistress at Cooran, where she was stationed for over 20 years, to Cracow, only a few days earlier. ¹⁶⁷

Mr J. R. Caldwell, who has been a patient in the Cracow Hospital with an unspecified condition, was discharged to recuperate in Rockhampton with his wife and family. ¹⁶⁸

Mrs Tierney was reported to be an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital, and Mrs Taylor had been discharged after having been a patient there for a prolonged period. Ages and conditions were not stated. ¹⁶⁹

Dr Jones attended two casualties at a football match played at Cracow against a team from Eidsvold, S. Collins took a bad toss resulting in a few days in the Cracow Hospital suffering from slight concussion. Maurice Hawkins received a broken collarbone and was allowed to go home after treatment. ¹⁷⁰

Dr J Hains attended the July meeting of the combined Eidsvold-Cracow Hospital Board. ¹⁷¹

Dr A. M. Jones visited the Theodore outpatients' department on alternate Tuesdays to support Dr Burke Gaffney of Baralaba who was also responsible for the Theodore centre. ¹⁷²

The October meeting of the Eidsvold-Cracow Hospital Board was held in the doctor's residence at Cracow. The doctor's presence is perhaps implied though not stated. ¹⁷³⁷

Mr R. Ahern, ambulance bearer and secretary, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a broken leg following an accident at the Plateau mine. When loading ore into a truck a big rock hit the truck, forcing it back on to his leg, which was broken below the knee. The fracture was set uneventfully. No further enquiry appears in the press.

Mr R. Harvey was also admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from abdominal trauma. Whilst leading two racehorses through a gate he was kicked in the stomach when one of the horses took fright and attempted to break away. He was taken to hospital and detained briefly for observation and discharged though still rather sick and sore. ^{174,175}

Dr Alice Muriel Jones discussed her career with the Courier Mail. She had experienced a challenging life. She was the eldest of the nine children of the late Mr and Mrs Cecil Wallace Lavarack and passed out first in her year in the Queensland High School state scholarships.

She graduated from Melbourne University in 1909, the only female in her year, in third place out of fifty-nine students. She became the first female resident doctor at Royal Melbourne Hospital. She then practiced in Muttaborra from 1910 to 1912 before her marriage.

These are outstanding intellectual and professional achievements in the era when female medical students were extremely rare and she must have had some high hurdles to overcome.

Dr Jones was replaced in Muttaborra by another stellar Melbourne University honours graduate and female medical practitioner, Laura Weir. ¹⁷⁶

Alice then retired to assist her husband running a mixed fruit orchard initially at Julia Creek, then at the Summit, near Stanthorpe. When widowed with six or seven children in 1931 shortly after the birth of her last child, she supported her

large young family and worked the orchard herself until there was a demand for doctors during the war and she decided in 1942 to give them a hand, accepting the position in Cracow after thirty years lost to medicine.

The health of Cracow's five hundred people had been her sole responsibility since 1942 and she had delivered a hundred babies since her return. Now aged sixty-five, she was assisted by the matron who usually had to do the cooking, and two junior nurses.

Her younger brother, Sir John Lavarack, was the Governor of Queensland. ¹⁷⁷

4.1.11. 1948

The younger brother of Dr A. M. Jones, Medical Superintendent of the Cracow Hospital, His Excellency the Governor, General Lavarack, accompanied by Lady Lavarack, proposed visiting Eidsvold in May to open the Centenary Show. ¹⁷⁸

Dr A. M. Jones was relieved by Dr Jean Fairbairn from Brisbane while on holiday in Brisbane and Stanthorpe herself. ¹⁷⁹

Dr A. M. Jones informed the health department that the last nurse had left to be married and that the hospital was left with the matron alone. Dr Jones also stated that she would have to leave shortly to undergo an operation and that Cracow Hospital which is in a well-populated area some distance from other hospitals should not be left without medical service. Dr Jones recommended with the support of the board that the Department of Health and Home Affairs should provide two doctors for adequate assistance to maintain current services. ¹⁸⁰

Dr. Alice Jones visited her brother, the Governor, and Lady Lavarack for luncheon at Government House. ¹⁸¹

Mr E. Ham was admitted to the Cracow Hospital following a motor vehicle accident when travelling home from Theodore. He had a miraculous escape from serious injury and was reported to be progressing favourably. ¹⁸²

Mrs M. Sollitt was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a painful infection of the hand. ¹⁸³

Dr. J. Hains led a motion protesting against the Queensland Health Department's proposed abolition of the Eidsvold - Cracow Hospitals Board. The rationale for this proposal and details of a future alternative structure were not published, though more autonomy for the Cracow health care professionals may be beneficial. ¹⁸⁴

The Queensland State Government's decision to abolish the Eidsvold-Cracow Hospitals Board was formally announced. ¹⁸⁵

4.1.12. 1949

Dr. Alice M. Jones resigned from Cracow Hospital having been resident doctor for seven years because of ill-health. The board secretary said last night that there was no suggestion of closing the Cracow hospitals because of staff resignations and that Dr Jones had so nobly held the post through trying times. The Herald noted that Cracow would now be without a medical officer, which was a grave concern considering its geographical isolation and the fact that it has a well-equipped modern hospital. ¹⁸⁶

Cracow Hospital advertised for a nursing sister available painting a rosy picture of conditions there and said that the duties would be light, as would be supported by the dwindling number of patients attending. ^{187,188}

In October 1949, Matron Morrison without any other trained staff was very ably coping with all Cracow Hospital patients. The hospital was still without a resident doctor and depended upon the fortnightly visit of Dr Channon from Mundubbera. ¹⁸⁹

G. Stockwell, the organiser, presumably of a union, writing for the Brisbane Worker visited many employment sites in the Monto district including Cracow Hospital to renew tickets and attend complaints. ¹⁹⁰

Dr Channon from Mundubbera was able to visit Cracow Hospital on a regular basis. Eighty-three inpatients had been treated for a total of four hundred and seventy-seven bed days. There had been eighteen ladies in the maternity ward giving birth to fourteen babies. There had been one thousand nine hundred and fifty-eight outpatient attendances. ¹⁹¹

4.1.13. 1950

At a local Country Women's Association meeting, Mrs. Baird stated that there was no doctor in Eidsvold and the hospital was closed, that Cracow Hospital was also closed and she had been told that the Mundubbera Hospital was also to be closed. She said this was an urgent matter and must be taken up with the council. Mrs Baird appears misinformed about the Cracow hospital being closed though it clearly had a period without a doctor. ¹⁹²

The press noted that a Mr W. Connellan has resumed duties at Cracow Hospital, after his annual holidays, however two years later he is reported to be the school bus driver, so a clinical role seems improbable. ¹⁹³

4.1.14. Dr. W K J Webb

Dr Channon visited Cracow Hospital from Mundubbera in late May and arrangements were made for Dr Webb, resident doctor of Eidsvold, to visit Cracow weekly in future. ¹⁹⁴

Wayne Keler and Eric Mossman were both admitted to the Cracow Hospital under Dr Webb. Keler had his hand caught in a belt badly crushing his fingers whilst starting the engine of a power saw. Eric Mossman was thrown from a horse on his property and probably fractured his leg. ¹⁹⁵

Mr W. Lawson was an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital. His age and diagnosis were not stated. ^{196, 197}

Mr J. Malcolm, a twenty-eight-year-old man, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having been knocked unconscious and had his teeth broken. There had been a disturbance in Cracow at a dance held in the Regent Theatre when a few non-white people attempted to gate-crash the dance and Malcolm asked them to leave. A fight broke out and Malcolm was hit with fists, boots and a bottle of beer. The hospital reported that he was progressing favourably.

Dr. William Kevin Joseph Webb, Medical Superintendent of Cracow Hospital, gave evidence at the criminal sittings of the Circuit Court before his Honour, Mr. Justice J. A. Shelley. John Barra and Horney Nebo, of Cracow, were charged that on July 1, 1953. at Cracow, they assaulted John David Malcolm, occasioning bodily harm.

Webb reported that he found bruises and abrasions when examining Malcolm. Fractures were excluded with an X-ray. Webb considered the injuries would interfere with Malcolm's comfort but were not serious.

Witnesses stated that the affray was commenced by Malcolm, and the Crown Prosecutor. Mr. A. D. Finn, guided by the judge entered a nolle prosequi instruction and the case was dismissed. ^{198,199}

Mr D. Robinson, Mr Abbott and Mr A. Du Payne were inpatients in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁰⁰

Mrs. R. Ahern was an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital and Mr A. Du Payne was still in hospital. ²⁰¹

Mrs K. Carmody was an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁰²

Dr Webb paid his weekly visit to Cracow. Mr Tynan was ill in the Cracow Hospital and Master Du Payne was still in hospital. ^{203,204}

Mr Alan Davis had been an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital. ²⁰⁵

4.1.15. 1951

Mr. M. Craufaud, the accountant at the Golden Plateau Mine, was recovering as an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital and hoped to be back in his position soon. However, although discharged two weeks later after several weeks in hospital, was still confined to his bed. Mr Coates, another inpatient of the Cracow Hospital had also been discharged. ^{206,207}

Archibald Gray, a Scotsman, was killed at the Klondyke Gold Mine, Cracow when a boulder fell on him. An inquest was held before Mr J. Ward, S.M., Maryborough. The Inspector of Mines at Rockhampton called six witnesses into the death of Gray at the Klondyke mine on December 21st 1950. The inevitable and usual findings of inquests into deaths in the mines was that Gray was accidentally killed. ^{208,209}

The citizens of Cracow were sorry to hear of the retirement from the hospital of Matron Morrison who had been for many years the mainstay of the Cracow Hospital when no resident doctor has been present. She had undergone a surgical operation and wished for a period of convalescence to make a speedy recovery. ²¹⁰

Dr. Burke Gaffney, visiting medical practitioner to Cracow and the Hospital for many years relocated his practice to Coorparoo in Brisbane. The Herald thought this would mean that the hospital would close as Cracow no longer had a doctor, and the nearest doctor and hospital were at Biloela seventy miles away, with impassable connecting roads in wet weather. ²¹¹

However, the next entry disproved the closure. Mr Jim Mills, one of the early gold prospectors in Cracow, died in Cracow Hospital after being in poor health for some time. He had leased the Sunrise Mine, with the late Mr A. Jarvis, which he subsequently sold to the Golden Plateau who were still working it. ²¹²

There was one suspected case of poliomyelitis in the Cracow Hospital. It was still a few more years before the vaccine became available. ²¹³

Mrs G. Hamilton had been an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital. ²¹⁴

The Cracow CWA secretary reported that the Cracow Hospital desperately needed children's pyjamas and members generously offered to make some. At the meeting it was announced that the branch had lost one of its faithful members, Matron Morrison. A letter of sympathy was sent to her relatives. That implication is that the previous matron had died and her operation was of a more severe nature than apparent. ²¹⁵

Mr J. Ryan and his daughter Jean were inpatients in the Cracow Hospital suffering from pneumonia. Miss Colleen Fry was also an inpatient and was expected to remain for a few more weeks. Mr John Waller slipped at the Golden Plateau mine and burnt his hand severely. Admission to hospital seemed probably though not stated. ²¹⁶

Mrs Jarvis was an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital. ²¹⁷

The Queensland Times noted Cracow and several other rural Hospitals continued to search for medical officers. The Charleville Flying Doctor, Dr. Allan Vickers considered that the main reasons why doctors would not go there the shortage of amenities in the outback and the environmental dust and bush fire smoke compared with the city and the surf of the South Coast. Educational opportunities for doctors' families were much better in Brisbane and solo practices afforded little time off duty. Private practices were much more lucrative than hospital salaries.

The Director-General of Health, Dr. Fryberg, said that the position should be considerably improved in 1952 with a record number of medical students graduating but failed to offer improved salaries or conditions as inducements. ²¹⁸

The Cracow citizens' committee appreciated that the salaries offered by the Cracow Hospital administration therefore were quite inadequate to attract nursing staff. A meeting was held to commence fund raising to offer a bonus to the nursing staff as an inducement for them to remain at Cracow Hospital. A swimming carnival was arranged at the Cracow weir as an initial fundraising function. ^{219,220}

4.1.16. 1952

Mr Burnett McGuire of Theodore, died in the Cracow Hospital from pneumonia. His age was not specified. Mrs Roaul Joyce was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having burnt her feet and legs with boiling fat but recovered to return home to Gyranda. Sylvia Chambers was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with acute appendicitis. It is not stated whether she had an appendectomy. ²²¹

Mrs Jack Ryan was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a nervous breakdown. Mrs Hunt, the postmistress, was admitted to hospital for several days. ²²²

Mr. F. Kendal was discharged home again after an admission to the Cracow Hospital for a couple of weeks with a poisoned band. ²²³

The ten bed Cracow Hospital was forced to close due to a shortage of staff although it served the whole Cracow-Theodore area. One of the hospital officials said tonight that it was impossible to get medical and nursing staff to go to Cracow. Patients would now have to go to Eidsvold sixty miles away. ²²⁴

The Cracow Citizens Committee considered that it should be possible to reopen the hospital with the assistance of Dr. Petersen, resident medical officer in Cracow and Nurse Molly Fry. Both were attending patients in town and in the hospital outpatients' department. The Cracow Citizens' Committee offered to pay both a matron and sister £20 at the end of six months' satisfactory and continuous service, paid from moneys subscribed by citizens of Cracow for this purpose. ²²⁵

Mr. Canning resumed duty as caretaker at the Cracow Hospital, presumably to keep the establishment ready for reopening. ²²⁶

Mr J. R. May, at a recent cattle sale at Eidsvold donated the proceeds from one of his beasts to the Cracow Hospital Nurses' Bonus Fund in preparation for the reopening. ²²⁷

Mrs Hotz was taken initially to the Cracow Hospital suffering concussion and severe shock following a motor vehicle accident. After attention by Dr Petersen, she was conveyed by ambulance to Monto Hospital.

A head-on collision had occurred about nine miles from Cracow on June 23rd. An Eidsvold bound roadster, driven by Mr T. Halliday, with Mrs E. Hotz as a passenger, collided on a bad ridge with a Cracow-bound utility, driven by Mr N. Silmon. The men received only minor injuries, but were also transferred to Monto Hospital after attendance by Dr Petersen. ²²⁸

The Cracow Hospital reopened on Friday 10th July after having been closed for at least ten weeks. According to the Herald, it closed on March 31st. Matron McMahon and Sister Low had been added to the staff to support Dr Petersen and Nurse Fry. A wide area, including Gamboon and Theodore now had hospital services again.

Mr Phil Morris, of Theodore, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with severe lacerations to his right leg. He had been riding a horse, which started to buck and play up, dragging his right leg along a wire fence. He was suffering from shock, but his condition was not considered serious. ^{229,230}

Mr A. Downs was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with knee and leg injuries sustained while playing football, ²³¹.

Mr J. Becker and Mr Phil Morris were discharged from Cracow Hospital to return home. Phil, who injured his 1 leg badly in a riding accident was still on crutches after a long stay in the Cracow Hospital. ²³²

John Hamilton, aged fourteen of Candoona Station, Camboon, was rushed to the Cracow Hospital after being bitten by a venomous snake. He was discharged the following morning without complications. Mr Doug Marshall was admitted to the Cracow Hospital for stitches having cut his leg while ringbarking. Mrs Don Hansen and Mrs Donnell and her baby, of Theodore were also admitted to hospital. Mr Hoffman, Mrs Bridgeman, sen., Mrs Hansen, sen., and Master Kevin Hansen, Mr Holmes and Blayne were all discharged from hospital. ²³³

A son was born to Mr and Mrs F. Potter in the Cracow Hospital. ²³⁴

The son of Mr and Mrs Cannell was seen in the Cracow Hospital for an X-Ray as he had been chewing razor blades. The son of Mr and Mrs Kimble from Theodore was taken to see the doctor.

Mr Peter Erb of Theodore was admitted to the Cracow Hospital in a serious condition as the result of a bad cut on his left leg with a circular saw. He and his brother George were cutting cord wood when the accident occurred. Latest reports are that he was progressing favourably, but he will be an inmate for some considerable time.

H. Horn, of Boughyard station, was driving his jeep on his property when he crashed into a railing fence, escaping with cuts on his face. Master Kevin Fry was admitted to the Cracow Hospital requiring the insertion of three stitches having cut his foot while playing.

Mr Ray Hart was seen in the Cracow Hospital with metal in his eyes but could be discharged home after treatment. ^{235,236}

Faye Barra, an eleven-year-old girl was admitted to the Cracow Hospital following an accident with an axe. While accompanying her father, who was ringbarking on Moorocaba Station approximately thirty miles from Cracow, she fell when running with an axe over her shoulder and severed three fingers. Her condition was as satisfactory as possible.

Allan Donald, aged nine, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with severe lacerations and abrasions having been knocked down by a car in the main street. A truck driven by Stewart Hutchison capsized on the Theodore-Woolton Road. W. Hutchison and H. Balchin, who were passengers, received lacerations to the head and arms. The driver escaped with a few bruises but the truck was very severely damaged. The Bulletin does not state if they were admitted to the Cracow Hospital.

Mrs Vic Myles of Theodore was admitted to the Cracow Hospital and Mr R. Brown remains an inpatient Mrs E. Slements and Mr S. Whitehead were discharged home, the former after a lengthy admission in the Cracow Hospital.²³⁸

Mrs Deverell, of Theodore, was recovering from an operation in the Cracow Hospital, and Miss Shirley Fry had been discharged.

Mr Charlie Clarke, an elderly resident of Cracow died suddenly in the Cracow Hospital. Mr Charles Schnell was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having fractured his wrist in a motor-cycle accident. Mr Douglas Horn was admitted to the hospital having cut his leg with an axe when scrubbing on his father's property. Mr Herb Horn was rushed to hospital suffering from blood poisoning.

George Daniells who came from Binda weir for the weekend, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital, Mr Walter Taffy O'Sullivan ran into a stationary car parked outside his store and was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a bruised leg and shock.^{239,240}

Master Trevor Francis was admitted to the Cracow Hospital, while Mr Charlie Schnell and Mr Doug Horn were discharged.²⁴¹

Mrs Patterson was an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital. Mr Ingram was discharged home to Theodore from the Cracow Hospital.²⁴²

Mr F. Hutchison remained an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital.²⁴³

The daughters of Mrs V. Davis and Mrs J. Morris were inpatients of the Cracow Hospital,

Mr Kathcart, Harold Hutchisons, of Camboon, Mrs B. Quinn and Messrs Jack Quail and W. Betteridge were also inpatients of the Cracow Hospital.²⁴⁴

Mrs A. G. Paterson was readmitted to the Cracow Hospital two days after discharge having been an inpatient for some weeks.²⁴⁵

Mrs Robinson was an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital.²⁴⁶

Mervyn Hewitt was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a head injury. While chasing a beast on the Rhyddings he was thrown against a tree. When he regained consciousness, he rode three miles home and was taken to hospital. His condition was not serious. Mrs E. Robinson was transferred to the Rockhampton Hospital.

The Herald noted that the Cracow Goldfield had now been mined for twenty years.²⁴⁷

Mrs E. Robinson was transferred from the Cracow Hospital to the Rockhampton Hospital, presumably for more specialised treatment. Miss Phyllis Horn was admitted to Cracow Hospital following a motorcycle accident.

Dr and Mrs Petersen returned to Cracow after a holiday.^{248, 249}

4.1.17. 1953

Miss Phyllis Horn who was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from bruises and shock following a motor cycle accident must have recovered well as she was a pianist at a social dinner party the following month.. She had been the pillion passenger when the motor cycle driven by John Waller punctured the rear tyre causing it to skid and hit a guide pole, smashing the front of the machine.^{250, 251}

Kelvin Morris, Helen Wheeler and Mrs Trousdal were inpatients of the Cracow Hospital, while Miss Betty Hope had been discharged home to Eidsvold.²⁵²

Mrs Edmunds had been discharged from the Cracow Hospital home to Theodore. ²⁵³

Mrs. C. Byrne and her baby daughter had been discharged from the Cracow Hospital. ²⁵⁴

The son of Mrs Field of Theodore was an inpatient of the Cracow Hospital. ²⁵⁵

The perils of the remote Australian bush were revealed by the discovery of the body of Mr D. Fuller in a waterhole near old Isla crossing, twenty-five miles from Theodore. Mr Fuller, who was a stockman employed in the Cracow-Theodore district for many years had been out mustering horses when his riderless horse was seen on a nearby property initiating a search.

After a two-day search led by Sergeant Lange, of Theodore, his body was found. His cause of death was not stated, he may have fallen from his horse, died of exposure and dehydration or even a snake bite. The police stated there were no suspicious circumstances raising the possibility of suicide. There was no subsequent post-mortem or inquest reported in the press.

Mr Stan Oakroot was admitted urgently to the Cracow Hospital with deep facial cuts caused when his utility skidded off the road on loose gravel and ran off the road into a tree smashing the windscreen. His condition was satisfactory but the vehicle was a complete wreck.

His two young male passengers escaped with only minor superficial injuries.

Miss Joan Sleep was discharged from the Cracow Hospital. ²⁵⁶

R. Gordon. G. Brown and Harold Bales all had to receive medical treatment for injuries received in a Theodore v. Moura football match and Gordon was detained in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁵⁷

Albert Booth Clarke, general manager of the Golden Plateau Mine at Cracow appeared at a sitting of the Court of Petty Sessions at Cracow before Mr Ward, SM, when charged with an offence under the Mines Regulations Acts. The complainant, Mr O. Andersen, inspector of mines, stated that he inspected the Golden Plateau Mine in December 1952, and noticed that the record book had not been entered up by the manager for weekly inspections for some considerable time. The manager had admitted he had not made regular inspections of the mine and in particular in December. He said he had been too busy to carry out inspections. Mr Andersen said the regulation required the manager of the mine to be fully qualified as a first-class mine manager and it was only by regular inspections that the workings could be kept under proper supervision and maintained in a safe state.

The defendant had been previously warned and the importance of regular inspections had been stressed. A serious view was taken of the offence and the penalty should be sufficient to impress upon the manager his responsibility under the Acts. Mr Ward fined the defendant £4, with 6/- costs. Mr Ward said the matter was serious because a life-threatening accident could occur through the workings becoming dangerous.

A plea of guilty was entered by the defendant who gave an undertaking to carry out regular inspections as required and said he had been making regular inspections since the visit of the Inspector in December. ²⁵⁸

Mr Neil Perry from Ballalaba was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from facial abrasions, a broken clavicle and other injuries sustained when he was thrown from his horse whilst riding the jumps at the Theodore show. The horse failed to make a clean jump, fell and rolled on Perry. It was stated that he was in a serious condition. ^{259, 260}

Ian Hunter, eldest son of Mr and Mrs E. Hunter, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having fractured his arm while playing football. Dr Blackburn attended over thirty patients at his weekly visit as there was much sickness in the district. ²⁶¹

Mr M. Craufurd was admitted to the Cracow Hospital. ²⁶²

Mr J. Grant was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from pneumonia. Mr Andrew William Abbott was admitted to the Cracow Hospital, suffering from lacerations to the head, arms, face and shoulder sustained when he fell from the pillion seat of a motorcycle in an accident on the Cracow-Taroom Road. ²⁶³

A daughter, Louise Vivian, was born to Mrs. L. Huth in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁶⁴

Mrs L. Huth, her daughter Louise Vivian and Mr M. Craufurd were discharged from the Cracow Hospital, while Mrs H. White, Mrs A. Darr and Master B. Allen were admitted. ²⁶⁵

Betty Huth, aged nineteen months, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital for a few having severed her little finger and cut the second finger of her left hand when playing with an axe near her brother who was splitting wood.

Mr P Cominsky broke his left arm and Mr R. Orava was knocked unconscious in an accident on the Cracow-Eidsvold Road. Mr C. Warren, driving a utility, skidded on gravel rounding a corner causing the vehicle to leave the road and hit a tree stump, causing damage to the front suspension. Warren was uninjured but presumably the other two required admission to the Cracow Hospital.

Mr Kehl was transported by ambulance from Taroom to the Cracow Hospital.

Mrs F. Oakroots was admitted to hospital suffering from blood pressure. ²⁶⁶

Mrs. J. Becker was discharged home from the Cracow Hospital while Mr. Donald Hall was admitted to the Cracow Hospital. ²⁶⁷

Mr. John Kehl, aged seventy-eight of Taroom, died in the Cracow Hospital a week after admission having been in poor health for a considerable time. ²⁶⁸

A baby daughter was born to Mrs. L. Leeon in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁶⁹

Mrs R. Dunbar was an inpatient in the Cracow Hospital. Mr C. Westmoreland was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a head injury. A wedge was dislodged at his sawmill and flew out, striking him on the side of the head. The injury was fortunately not severe, and he was discharged after a few days. Flu, measles and mumps were very prevalent in town. ^{270, 271}

The Cracow Citizens' Committee called a public meeting to decide whether the public wished to raise funds to pay a bonus to the nursing staff. Predictably this had widespread support as the low salaries offered did little to entice qualified sisters to Cracow. ²⁷²

Delores Du Payne, the youngest daughter of Mr and Mrs A. Du Payne aged twenty-three months was admitted as an emergency to the Cracow Hospital when it was discovered that she had eaten an unknown quantity of tablets prescribed for her brother. After being placed on the seriously ill list for two days, she recovered uneventfully and was discharged home. ²⁷³

Mrs. P. Earl and Miss Margaret Townsend were both inpatients in the Cracow Hospital but both were reported to be improving. ²⁷⁴

T. Dennis, Union Organiser visited Cracow hospital and on checking whether employees had been paid for Coronation Day at overtime rates, it was found that they had not. However, payment was promised to be made up in the next pay. ²⁷⁵

Mrs P. Earl and Miss M. Townsend were discharged home from the Cracow Hospital. ²⁷⁶

4.1.18. 1954

Mr Mark Sollet, an old resident of the district, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital when he became suddenly ill at the Theodore Show. ²⁷⁷

Mr. J. Ford was transported from the Cracow Hospital to the Maryborough General Hospital by ambulance for further medical attention. ²⁷⁸

J. Clark, an employee of the Main Roads Commission, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from severe bruises to the back and legs and shock. The bulldozer he was driving got out of control and he was thrown to the ground. ²⁷⁹

Mr W. Hutchison of Woolton was admitted to the Cracow Hospital where he was reported to be improving. Mr E. H. Tunny was admitted to the Cracow Hospital requiring a plaster for a severely crushed foot sustained when a light pole

fell on it. He improved rapidly and was discharged within a fortnight though he still required crutches. Mr Cocks also required a plaster in the Cracow Hospital having broken his ankle while playing football. ^{280,281}

Alan du Payne was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having swallowed a marble. X-Ray revealed the marble to be in his stomach and Alan was symptom free. Natural passage without problems was anticipated.

Mr. L. Donovan, clearing contractor, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital when his foot was crushed under a plant he was operating, severing one toe. ²⁸²

Mrs Abbott and Miss Anita Grambower of Cracow, and Mrs D. Munro of Theodore were admitted to the Cracow Hospital. ²⁸³

Miss Sandra Cameron and Mr. Tunny were discharged from the Cracow Hospital though the later was still on crutches. ²⁸⁴

A daughter was born to Mrs W. Stillaway in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁸⁵

A daughter was born in the Cracow Hospital to Mrs R. Krehea. The hospital staff had been busy owing to the large number of residents admitted with influenza. ²⁸⁶

Mrs. J. Milliard's infant son was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having drunk some kerosene but was reported to be out of danger now.

Max Daley was also admitted to the Cracow Hospital having cut his foot while ringbarking, and severed a toe. Influenza remained very prevalent in town. ²⁸⁷

Christine Gail, a daughter for Mrs Munkton of Theodore, was born in the Cracow Hospital.

Mr. Thomas Dent, an elderly resident died in the Cracow Hospital having been ill for some time. He had been employed by Mr. G. Sewell for many years. ²⁸⁸

Mrs H. Jones was an inpatient in the Cracow District Hospital. ^{289, 290}

Messrs Hillhouse and A. James were admitted to the Cracow Hospital following a motor vehicle accident. James was suffering from abrasions, a large cut on the head and shock and Hillhouse from shock. Superintendent Hillhouse was driving the Theodore ambulance back from Cracow when it crashed and capsized. Hillhouse's son, James, was also in the vehicle but was unhurt. The ambulance was extensively damaged and was towed to Theodore for repairs.

Mrs J. Hinder had been admitted to the Cracow Hospital but progressing satisfactorily and hoped to be discharged home soon. Measles and mumps were prevalent in the area. Several Theodore residents were patients in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁹¹

Mr F. Shelton was admitted to Cracow Hospital where eight stitches were inserted into a scalp wound. When preparing to inflate the back tyre of his truck the rim flew from the wheel lacerating the left side of his head.

Mrs H Jones and Mrs S. Oakroot were inpatients in the Cracow Hospital. ²⁹²

Mrs and Miss Mary Bloomfield were admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from severe abrasions and shock following a motor vehicle accident in which the car skidded, left the road and collided with a tree. The car was extensively damaged.

Mrs P. Walsh, manageress or the Hotel Theodore, was an inpatient in the Cracow Hotel. ²⁸⁷

Mrs Vidler was a patient in Cracow Hospital. Mr J. Morris fractured his wrist when he was thrown out of a car in an accident but appears not to have required admission. ²⁹³

Frederick Potter, aged about forty, and Kerry Patrick Woodroffe, aged twenty-one were killed instantly by an explosion in the Golden Plateau gold mine at Cracow. The men were working together in a shaft 350 ft deep and none of the other miners heard the blast, which badly mutilated and killed them both instantly.

The police stated that Potter and Woodroffe had set and exploded charges in the shaft the previous night. It was believed that one charge did detonate but exploded after the men returned to the shaft yesterday morning and resumed work. Police said it was the first fatal underground accident in the mine, which has been operating for about twenty years. The last fatality on the field was in December 1950, when a man was killed in the Klondyke Mine.

Both men were married with one child, Woodroffe's wife was still in the Cracow Hospital after the birth of her first child, a son, a few days earlier. Woodroffe had arrived in Cracow about six weeks ago and since then had been working with Potter, a resident of Cracow for many years.

The Inspector of Mines from Rockhampton, Mr Anderson, will motor to Cracow to join the Cracow mine's check inspector, Mr Purcell, in investigating the tragedy.^{294,295}

Mr A. Clarke, the manager of the Golden Plateau Mine and Mr McNab, a director of the company commenced a widows fund for Mrs Potter and Mrs Woodroffe with a very substantial donation. The employees and staff of the Golden Plateau Mine each donated one shift's pay towards the fund and the business people and citizens of Cracow also gave substantial donations. The sum of £368 was collected and equally shared between the two widows. Inflation between 1954 and 2023 is a factor of just over twenty giving a compensation of about \$15,000 Australian, one suspects the widows may have taken in washing and ironing!

There was no further inquiry or compensation published in the Queensland press.²⁹¹

John Frances McNalty, an eighty-one-year-old veteran died in the Cracow District Hospital three hours after being admitted following a motor vehicle incident in which he was accidentally knocked down by a utility driven by Mr S. Oakroot.²⁹⁷

Mrs J. Vidler and Mr Vince Collins were both discharged home from the Cracow Hospital having been inpatients for some weeks, Collins back to Brisbane. Mr Stan Letchford who was also an inpatient in Cracow Hospital was discharged.

Measles and influenza were prevalent in Cracow at the time.²⁹⁸

Master Phillip Grambower was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with head injuries sustained in a car crash. The accident occurred on the Cracow-Eidsvold Road when a car driven by Mr George Rickett, of Cracow, struck a guidepost. Mr Rickett and son, John, were each treated for lacerations to the head but did not require admission.²⁹⁹

4.1.19. 1955

Clynton Rose was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a dislocated right hip and severe head lacerations and abrasions following an accident that occurred on the Theodore-Cracow Road. A motor car, driven by Thomas Davis and a motorcycle, ridden by Rose collided, also causing severe damage to the motorcycle and lesser damage to the motor car.

There is a great deal of sickness in the town. Measles was very prevalent and several residents are patients in the Cracow Hospital.³⁰⁰

Messrs C. C. Anderson and J. Vidler of the commission staff were admitted to the Cracow Hospital. Several people suffering from septic throats had also been admitted to hospital as the disease was prevalent in the area.³⁰¹

Mr J. Theodore, contractor, and two of his men were admitted to the Cracow Hospital following a serious car accident sixteen miles from Cracow on the Cracow-Eidsvold Road when enroute to Bundaberg. The truck in which they were travelling struck a guidepost on a grid and crashed into a tree on the side of the road. It was completely wrecked.

John Theodore, a forty-six-year-old married man of Bundaberg had severe lacerations to the head, throat, face and neck. Phillip Hampton, a thirty-five-year-old single man and Alan Hooper, a forty-three-year-old married man both of Bundaberg had multiple fractures. All were said to be in a serious condition.^{302, 303}

Mr Les Hunter was conveyed to the Cracow Hospital suffering from concussion, multiple lacerations and bruises and a fractured leg.³⁰⁴

Mrs Oakroot, aged seventy-four, died in the Cracow Hospital having been in poor health for some time. She was widowed seven years previously and was survived by her only son. She had been resident in Cracow for over twenty years.³⁰⁵

Don Hillhouse, aged fifteen, was admitted to the Cracow Hospital having been kicked in the face by a horse.³⁰⁶

Dr Alice Muriel Jones died in Brisbane on June 30th 1955. A son was born to Mr and Mrs S Grant in the Cracow District Hospital.³⁰⁷

The Herald noted that Cracow Hospital had been practically full of patients from Theodore more than once for some weeks and that there were still several Theodore patients in the hospital.^{308, 309}

A daughter was born to Mr and Mrs L. Huth in the Cracow Hospital.

Mr W. Horn of Glen View, Camboon, Mr R. Keller, Mr O. Jorgensen, Mr D. Clancy and Miss Colleen Fry were inpatients.³¹⁰

Mr S. Wilson was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a fractured leg sustained when his horse fell on him. Mr C. Westmoreland was admitted to the Cracow Hospital with a deep laceration of his hand sustained at the sawmill. Mrs H. Heron was admitted with scalds suffered whilst washing. Mrs Fleetwood had been discharged and was convalescing at home.

The Herald opined that Theodore needed a hospital, as at that moment there were eight residents of Theodore in Cracow Hospital and many more travelled to Cracow to consult the doctor.³¹¹

Mrs Barnes was an inpatient in the Cracow District Hospital.³¹²

Russell Douglas, a son for Mr and Mrs R Hamilton was born in the Cracow District Hospital.³¹³

Ray Tiegs was admitted to the Cracow Hospital suffering from a fractured leg, severe lacerations and shock sustained in an accident on the Boulevards when two motor cycles collided. His pillion rider Vernon Camp was not injured. The other motorcycle, ridden by Herbert Sollett was badly damaged but Sollett escaped with only a few abrasions.

G. Day had to have several sutures inserted into a scalp laceration sustained when he struck his head when diving from the springboard at the weir.³¹⁴

Noel Keller, aged eight, was admitted to the Cracow District Hospital having broken his foot when he fell over a block of wood. Karen Leigh, a daughter was born to Mr and Mrs C. Byrnes in the Cracow District Hospital.³¹⁵

Mrs I. Woods was discharged from the Cracow Hospital.³¹⁶

4.1.20. 1956

The final entry in a Trove search for articles in the Queensland Press with the search term 'Cracow Hospital' during the period 1930 – 2022 revealed that the hospital was again without a matron or sister. It was hoped that this position would soon be filled as the hospital did wonderful work in the district and is often taxed to capacity coping with patients seeking medical aid.^{317, 318}

Dr J. E. Petersen, who had already left Cracow, finally severed his remaining connection with the district by resigning as medical officer of health to the council for No. 1 division.³¹⁸

5. Case Load Summary 1932-1956

5.1. Mine accidents

Details of twelve mining accidents were published, four were fatal and not all the others required hospital admission. The fatal injuries appear not to have been the subject of an inquiry, none of them. There were inquiries into two of the lesser mining traumatic events and they were deemed 'accidents', commencing the Cracow mining series of failing to identify dangerous system hazards or to provide compensation, a feature in common with all Australian Mines

Albert Booth Clarke, general manager of the Golden Plateau Mine was found guilty in 1952 of an offence under the Mines Regulations Acts at a sitting of the Court of Petty Sessions.

Mr O. Andersen, inspector of mines, stated the Golden Plateau Mine weekly safety inspections record book had not been entered up by the manager for some considerable time. Clarke said he had been too busy to carry out safety inspections!

251

This seems a typical example of the concern shown by those in offices above ground for those below ground earning them a fortune. Clarke was fined £4! A contrast with the value of gold extracted from the mines of Cracow, some two billion dollars in today's currency. Little further comment appears required!

5.2. Rural accidents

Twenty-one people, male and female, young and old suffered trauma of variable severity from incidents involving horses.

Ten suffered accidental injuries from axes and four from power saws. Several of the injuries including amputation of finger and toes happened to unsupervised infants playing with razor-sharp axes.

Two men were lost in the bush, one of whom died. The bush is a very hostile environment for the unprepared. One man was admitted having been attacked by a fortunately dehorned bull and another by a cow. One was burnt in a bush fire, one bitten by a snake and one injured by a falling tree.

Several men had injuries from playing football including one broken leg and two men were injured in fights. Three gunshot injuries occurred with the common feature of having loaded guns when they were not about to be used immediately.

5.3. Motor vehicle accidents

Twenty-nine men, women and children were injured in motor vehicle accidents, two fatally.

5.4. Deaths

There were twenty-seven identified deaths in Cracow over the studied period of twenty-two years. Most were elderly after lengthy periods of ill-health. Six suffered fatal accidents on the road or in the mines, Three children died with burns, mostly unsupervised. Two women experienced immediate post-partum death. There was one murder and one peri-operative death.

5.5. Infectious diseases

One case each of diphtheria, poliomyelitis and scarlet fever were admitted. There were outbreaks of the now preventable Mumps, Measles and Chicken Pox

5.6. Obstetrics

Numbers of births were only recorded some of the time in the hospital monthly figures. At least sixty-two babies were born in Cracow Hospital with only one recorded neonatal death and one pair of twins. Parents were only identified individually from 1952. The first recorded inpatient in March 1938 was a mother giving birth and deliveries were occurring till September 1955, almost up to the hospital closure date. An important component of the clinical workload indicative of the many families living in Cracow during the peak mining period.

5.6.1. 2005

Local residents purchased the former Cracow District Hospital & restored it to its original condition. The hospital morgue was relocated to the front grounds of the Cracow Museum. In recent years, the former hospital has been used as accommodation for Cracow gold mining employees.

6. Conclusion

Cracow Hospital served as a community hospital for some twenty years while the mines flourished.

From an internal medical viewpoint, few details are given of medical diseases, diagnoses of hospitalised patients or causes of death and treatments prescribed, though the era is notable for the increasing availability of antibiotics. Further comment is not possible.

However, the newspapers give details of injuries received in accidents enabling analysis and comment. Injuries from motor vehicles and from horses are similar in number as befits that period in a rural area.

Unsupervised children were at risk of potentially fatal burns and loss of digits when playing with axes. Infectious viral diseases occurred in sporadic epidemics in Cracow, conditions that are now optional depending on vaccine compliance.

The author has written of other hospitals based in mining communities, Maytown and Mungana in North Queensland, Kalgoorlie and Big Bell in Western Australia and Zeehan in Tasmania though only Kalgoorlie Hospital remains open with a modern hospital building, a still functioning mine and thriving population. The other towns depopulated, Mungana, Maytown and Big Bell are now ghost towns, Zeehan has a small residual population around seven hundred having once had ten thousand inhabitants. These four all have reopened mines, a tribute to the geological skills of the early prospectors.^{320,321,322,323,324}

The Medical profession has long had a strong interest in safety and system analysis, particularly in morbidity and mortality and in medication safety in the twenty-first century. The author appreciates the mining era examined was some seven decades earlier but looks for safety analysis and activity in that period.^{325,326}

Maytown Hospital opened in 1876 and closed in 1893. Mining accidents occurred but inquiries and compensation were not recorded in the press.

Mungana Hospital opened in about 1906 and burnt down in 1928. There were inquiries into mine fatalities but the verdicts were uniformly that death was accidental and no one was to blame.

Zeehan was noted for the Mount Lyell Fire in 1912 in which forty-two men died. A Royal Commission determined that this was an accident and the mine owners were in no way responsible. The absence of an alarm system, the absence of water hoses or firefighting equipment, and the absence of a second shaft for emergency escapes were not seen as dangerous system or site flaws. Juries at mining death inquiries were generally able to reach a verdict of 'accident' within half an hour without retiring.

Big Bell Hospital was open from 1941 to 1955. All fatal and non-fatal accidents, whether in the mines, on the roads, or elsewhere were deemed accidental with no blame attached to any company or individual. The concept of compensation for widows and families was yet to come even though Workers' Compensation legislation dates back to the early days of the twentieth century.

Perhaps the author is an optimist. Even in 2021 miners are killed and maimed in mines with a total failure to hold administration culpable for ensuring safety or to identify any responsible individuals. Graham Dawson was killed in 2021 in a roof fall incident at the Sojitz Gregory Coal Mine when there was some previous evidence of weakness in the roof. Five miners were severely burned at the Grosvenor Mine by a gas explosion when a board of inquiry found that the Anglo-American Company knew of gas accumulation in the mine.

To date no charges of culpability or responsibility have been laid against mine owners.

Collectively these past and present mines earned multi billions of dollars' worth of coal, gold and other minerals. As today the benefits were almost exclusively for the business sector. The miners worked underground in dangerous confined spaces with no recompense for work-related trauma. Safety systems were minimal.

The doctors prepared to work in those environments earned some \$600 in the 1950s and nurses significantly less. In that era as today the brightest school leavers with the highest level of training working the longest hours for the good of society received much lower wages than those working in the upper levels of business, the most selfish of human endeavours. Property dealing is still today more remunerative than gaining a Nobel prize in Medicine!

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

Acknowledgments must be inserted here.

References

- [1] Morning Bulletin 7/3/1933
- [2] Central Queensland Herald 26/1/1933
- [3] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnet Advertiser 1/2/1933
- [4] Evening News 7/2/1933
- [5] Evening News 5/5/1933
- [6] Morning Bulletin 3/7/1933
- [7] The Courier Mail 7/12/1933
- [8] Townsville Daily Bulletin 12/12/1933
- [9] Toowoomba Chronicle and Darling Downs Gazette 30/12/1933
- [10] The Evening Telegraph 4/4/1916
- [11] Morning Bulletin 29/9/1929
- [12] Morning Bulletin 27/1/1934
- [13] The Telegraph 15/9/1934
- [14] Truth 16/9/1934
- [15] The Telegraph 12/10/1934
- [16] The Courier Mail 17/10/1934
- [17] Evening News 7/11/1934
- [18] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnet Advertiser 7/11/1934
- [19] Worker 14/11/1934
- [20] Morning Bulletin 21/1/1935
- [21] Townsville Daily Bulletin 7/2/1935
- [22] Central Queensland Herald 7/2/1935
- [23] Townsville Daily Bulletin 25/4/1935
- [24] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnet Advertiser 11/6/1935
- [25] Morning Bulletin 1/8/1935
- [26] Worker 10/12/1935
- [27] The Courier Mail 23/1/1936
- [28] Morning Bulletin 29/2/1936
- [29] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnet Advertiser 14/2/1936
- [30] The Telegraph 12/8/1936
- [31] Courier Mail 12/1/1937
- [32] Central Queensland Herald 25/3/1937
- [33] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnet Advertiser 26/5/1937

- [34] The Telegraph 17/6/1937
- [35] Central Queensland Herald 16/9/1937
- [36] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 8/12/1937
- [37] Courier Mail 18/1/1938
- [38] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 16/2/1938
- [39] Morning Bulletin 25/3/1938
- [40] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 16/5/1938
- [41] The Evening News 23/5/1939
- [42] Central Queensland Herald 28/6/1938
- [43] The Morning Bulletin 17/9/1938
- [44] Morning Bulletin 17/12/1938
- [45] Townsville Daily Bulletin 4/3/1939
- [46] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 4/1/1939
- [47] Courier Mail 8/2/1939
- [48] Townsville Daily Bulletin 10/2/1939
- [49] Morning Bulletin 20/2/1939
- [50] Morning Bulletin 10/3/1939
- [51] The Morning Bulletin 4/1/1939
- [52] Morning Bulletin 11/3/1939
- [53] Central Queensland Herald 11/5/1939
- [54] Morning Bulletin 20/5/1939
- [55] Morning Bulletin 3/6/1939
- [56] Townsville Daily Bulletin 15/6/1939
- [57] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 23/6/1939
- [58] Townsville Daily Bulletin 23/6/1939
- [59] Courier Mail 23/6/1939
- [60] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 25/10/1939
- [61] Central Queensland Herald 2/11/1939
- [62] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 26/6/1939
- [63] Central Queensland Herald 29/6/1939 Morning Bulletin 26/6/1939
- [64] Morning Bulletin 25/8/1939
- [65] Northern Miner 6/9/1939
- [66] Central Queensland Herald 7/9/1939
- [67] Morning Bulletin 11/9/1939
- [68] Morning Bulletin 26/9/1939
- [69] Evening News 1/11/1939
- [70] Central Queensland Herald 23/11/1939
- [71] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 18/12/1939
- [72] Townsville Daily Bulletin 4/3/1939

- [73] Morning Bulletin 6/12/1939,
- [74] Taylor R, Lewis M, Powles J The Australian mortality decline: all-cause mortality 1788–1990 *ANZ J Pub Health*. 1998; 2 (1):27-36
- [75] Courier Mail 12/1/1940
- [76] Queensland Times 14/2/1940
- [77] Morning Bulletin 29/1/1940
- [78] Courier Mail 20/2/1940
- [79] The Evening News 27/2/1940
- [80] The Telegraph 27/2/1940
- [81] Townsville Daily Bulletin 9/3/1940
- [82] Daily Mercury 15/9/1939
- [83] Morning Bulletin 9/3/1940
- [84] Evening News 19/4/1940
- [85] Morning Bulletin 20/5/1940
- [86] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 20/6/1940
- [87] Morning Bulletin 1/7/1940
- [88] Courier Mail 5/7/1940
- [89] Morning Bulletin 10/7/1940
- [90] Morning Bulletin 17/8/1940
- [91] The Telegraph 26/8/1940
- [92] Morning Bulletin 31/8/1940
- [93] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 25/9/1940
- [94] The Morning Bulletin 4/10/1940
- [95] The Central Queensland Herald 24/10/1940
- [96] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 6/11/1940
- [97] Morning Bulletin 6/2/1941
- [98] Morning Bulletin 26/2/1941
- [99] The Central Queensland Herald 27/2/1941
- [100] Morning Bulletin 1/4/1941
- [101] Queensland Country Life 17/4/1941
- [102] Courier Mail 7/5/1941
- [103] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 29/5/1941
- [104] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 15/7/1941
- [105] The Central Queensland Herald 31/7/1941
- [106] Central Queensland Herald 18/9/1941
- [107] Morning Bulletin 6/12/1941
- [108] Morning Bulletin 6/3/1942
- [109] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 4/4/1942
- [110] Morning Bulletin 11/4/1942
- [111] Morning Bulletin 16/4/1942

- [112] Central Queensland Herald 2/7/1942
- [113] Morning Bulletin 2/7/1942
- [114] Central Queensland Herald 20/8/1945
- [115] Morning Bulletin 23/10/1942
- [116] Courier Mail 6/11/1942
- [117] The Central Queensland Herald 4/2/1943
- [118] The Morning Bulletin 5/2/1943
- [119] The Central Queensland Herald 11/2/1943
- [120] The Central Queensland Herald 25/3/1943
- [121] The Central Queensland Herald 8/7/1943
- [122] The Morning Bulletin 14/9/1943
- [123] The Central Queensland Herald 11/11/1943
- [124] The Central Queensland Herald 16/12/1943
- [125] The Central Queensland Herald 9/3/1944
- [126] Central Queensland Herald 16/3/1944
- [127] Central Queensland Herald 18/5/1944
- [128] Morning Bulletin 24/5/1944
- [129] The Morning Bulletin 24/5/1944
- [130] Maryborough Chronicle, Wide Bay and Burnett Advertiser 31/5/1944
- [131] The Morning Bulletin 23/6/1944
- [132] The Morning Bulletin 18/7/1944
- [133] The Central Queensland Herald 17/8/1944
- [134] The Morning Bulletin 18/9/1944
- [135] Morning Bulletin 12/10/1944
- [136] The Central Queensland Herald 26/10/1944
- [137] Morning Bulletin 15/12/1944
- [138] Morning Bulletin 3/3/1945
- [139] Morning Bulletin 29/3/1945
- [140] The Courier Mail 29/3/1945
- [141] Morning Bulletin 12/5/1945
- [142] The Central Queensland Herald 31/5/1945
- [143] The Telegraph 12/6/1945
- [144] Morning Bulletin 7/6/1945
- [145] The Central Queensland Herald 7/7/1945
- [146] Morning Bulletin 16/7/1945
- [147] Morning Bulletin 16/8/1945
- [148] Sunday Mail 7/10/1945
- [149] The Central Queensland Herald 11/10/1945
- [150] The Central Queensland Herald 31/1/1946

- [151] Morning Bulletin 21/3/1946
- [152] Morning Bulletin 2/4/1946
- [153] Morning Bulletin 27/4/1946
- [154] Morning Bulletin 30/4/1946
- [155] The Courier Mail 16/5/1946
- [156] The Central Queensland Herald 6/6/1946
- [157] The Central Queensland Herald 1/8/1946
- [158] Morning Bulletin 1/11/1946
- [159] Morning Bulletin 30/11/1946
- [160] Central Queensland Herald 5/12/1946
- [161] Morning Bulletin 21/2/1947
- [162] Morning Bulletin 22/2/1947
- [163] Truth 12/1/1947
- [164] Morning Bulletin 9/5/1947
- [165] The Central Queensland Herald 29/5/1947
- [166] The Central Queensland Herald 12/6/1947
- [167] The Morning Bulletin 1/8/1947
- [168] The Morning Bulletin 19/8/1947
- [169] Maryborough Chronicle 20/10/1947
- [170] The Central Queensland Herald 30/10/1947 175 Morning Bulletin 31/10/1947
- [171] Stride P Springsure Hospital 1864-1939: The Original Springsure Hospital and the Doctors and Diseases. *J Biogen Sci Res* 5/12/2020
- [172] Courier Mail 18/12/1947
- [173] Maryborough Chronicle 30/1/1948
- [174] Central Queensland Herald 25/3/1948
- [175] Maryborough Chronicle 30/4/1948
- [176] Brisbane Telegraph 14/7/1948
- [177] The Central Queensland Herald 19/8/1948
- [178] The Central Queensland Herald 9/9/1948
- [179] Maryborough Chronicle 22/11/1948
- [180] Maryborough Chronicle 22/11/1948
- [181] The Courier Mail 19/2/1949
- [182] Maryborough Chronicle 31/3/1949
- [183] The Central Queensland Herald 5/5/1949
- [184] The Central Queensland Herald 13/10/1949
- [185] Worker 19/12/1949
- [186] The Morning Bulletin 26/8/1949
- [187] Maryborough Chronicle 18/2/1950
- [188] Morning Bulletin 12/5/1950
- [189] The Morning Bulletin 25/5/1950

- [190] Morning Bulletin 23/6/1950
- [191] The Central Queensland Herald 29/6/1950
- [192] The Morning Bulletin 3/7/1950
- [193] Central Queensland Herald 6/7/1950
- [194] Maryborough Chronicle 5/11/1950
- [195] Central Queensland Herald 13/7/1950
- [196] Central Queensland Herald 27/7/1950
- [197] The Morning Bulletin 22/9/1950
- [198] Central Queensland Herald 28/9/1950
- [199] The Morning Bulletin 6/10/1950
- [200] Central Queensland Herald 23/11/1950
- [201] Central Queensland Herald 1/1/1951
- [202] The Morning Bulletin 16/2/1951
- [203] The Morning Bulletin 5/1/1951
- [204] The Morning Bulletin 12/3/1951
- [205] Central Queensland Herald 15/3/1951
- [206] Central Queensland Herald 26/4/1951
- [207] Central Queensland Herald 19/7/1951
- [208] Central Queensland Herald 23/8/1951
- [209] Central Queensland Herald 6/9/1951
- [210] Central Queensland Herald 20/9/1951
- [211] Central Queensland Herald 25/10/1951
- [212] Central Queensland Herald 15/11/1951
- [213] Queensland Times 24/11/1951
- [214] Central Queensland Herald 13/12/1951
- [215] The Morning Bulletin 14/12/1951
- [216] The Morning Bulletin 21/1/1952
- [217] Central Queensland Herald 7/2/1952
- [218] The Morning Bulletin 18/2/1952
- [219] Central Queensland Herald 20/3/1952
- [220] Queensland Times 27/2/1952
- [221] Maryborough Chronicle 7/4/1952
- [222] Central Queensland Herald 24/4/1952
- [223] The Morning Bulletin 8/6/1952
- [224] Central Queensland Herald 3/7/1953
- [225] Central Queensland Herald 5/6/1952
- [226] Central Queensland Herald 17/7/1952
- [227] Central Queensland Herald 31/7/1952
- [228] The Morning Bulletin 19/8/1952

- [229] Central Queensland Herald 21/8/1952
- [230] Central Queensland Herald 28/8/1952
- [231] The Morning Bulletin 29/8/1952
- [232] Central Queensland Herald 4/9/1952
- [233] The Morning Bulletin 4/9/1952
- [234] The Morning Bulletin 22/9/1952
- [235] The Morning Bulletin 27/9/1952
- [236] Central Queensland Herald 2/10/1952
- [237] The Morning Bulletin 13/10/1952
- [238] The Morning Bulletin 28/10/1952
- [239] The Morning Bulletin 4/11/1952
- [240] Central Queensland Herald 13/11/1952
- [241] The Morning Bulletin 17/11/1952
- [242] The Morning Bulletin 4/12/1952
- [243] Central Queensland Herald 11/12/1952
- [244] The Morning Bulletin 12/12/1952
- [245] Central Queensland Herald 12/2/1953
- [246] The Morning Bulletin 13/3/1953
- [247] Central Queensland Herald 19/2/1953
- [248] The Morning Bulletin 6/3/1953
- [249] The Morning Bulletin 13/3/1953
- [250] Central Queensland Herald 26/3/1953
- [251] The Morning Bulletin 24/4/1953
- [252] The Morning Bulletin 1/5/1953
- [253] The Morning Bulletin 2/5/1953
- [254] The Morning Bulletin 21/5/1953
- [255] Central Queensland Herald 21/5/1953
- [256] The Morning Bulletin 7/7/1953
- [257] The Morning Bulletin 14/7/1953
- [258] The Morning Bulletin 27/8/1953
- [259] The Morning Bulletin 3/9/1953
- [260] The Morning Bulletin 11/9/1953
- [261] The Morning Bulletin 9/10/1953
- [262] The Morning Bulletin 16/10/1953
- [263] The Morning Bulletin 17/10/1953
- [264] Central Queensland Herald 5/11/1953
- [265] Morning Bulletin 6/11/1953
- [266] Central Queensland Herald 12/11/1953
- [267] Central Queensland Herald 19/11/1953

- [268] Central Queensland Herald 10/12/1953
- [269] The Morning Bulletin 17/12/1953
- [270] Brisbane Worker 21/12/1953
- [271] Central Queensland Herald 31/12/1953
- [272] The Morning Bulletin 1/1/1954
- [273] The Morning Bulletin 11/3/1954
- [274] Central Queensland Herald 22/4/1954
- [275] The Morning Bulletin 27/5/1954
- [276] Central Queensland Herald 10/6/1954
- [277] The Morning Bulletin 2/7/1954
- [278] The Morning Bulletin 21/7/1954
- [279] Central Queensland Herald 29/7/1954
- [280] Morning Bulletin 2/8/1954
- [281] The Morning Bulletin 6/8/1954
- [282] The Morning Bulletin 13/8/1954
- [283] Morning Bulletin 17/8/1954
- [284] The Morning Bulletin 8/9/1954
- [285] Central Queensland Herald 16/9/1954
- [286] Central Queensland Herald 7/10/1954
- [287] The Morning Bulletin 14/10/1954
- [288] Central Queensland Herald 4/11/1954
- [289] Maryborough Chronicle 8/12/1954
- [290] Central Queensland Herald 9/12/1954
- [291] The Morning Bulletin 29/12/1954
- [292] The Morning Bulletin 10/12/1954
- [293] The Morning Bulletin 14/12/1954
- [294] Central Queensland Herald 23/12/1954
- [295] Central Queensland Herald 6/1/1955
- [296] Central Queensland Herald 3/2/1955
- [297] Central Queensland Herald 17/2/1955
- [298] Central Queensland Herald 24/2/1955
- [299] Central Queensland Herald 24/2/1955
- [300] Central Queensland Herald 17/3/1955
- [301] Central Queensland Herald 9/6/1955
- [302] Central Queensland Herald 7/7/1955
- [303] Central Queensland Herald 14/7/1955
- [304] Central Queensland Herald 21/4/1955
- [305] Central Queensland Herald 21/7/1955
- [306] Central Queensland Herald 28/7/1955

- [307] Central Queensland Herald 1/9/1955
- [308] Central Queensland Herald 22/9/1955
- [309] Central Queensland Herald 13/10/1955
- [310] Central Queensland Herald 3/11/1955
- [311] Central Queensland Herald 17/11/1955
- [312] Central Queensland Herald 5/1/1956
- [313] Central Queensland Herald 1/3/1956
- [314] Central Queensland Herald 5/3/1956
- [315] Stride P Big Bell Hospital, 1941-1955 *Annals Clin Med Case Reports Historical Study* ISSN 2639-8109 Volume 10
- [316] Stride P. Kalgoorlie Hospital, Western Australia 1895-1897, the First Five Months of Hospital Admissions, and Typhoid in the Gold Fields. *J Environ Soc Sci.* 2015;2(2): 116.
- [317] Stride P Mungana and the Mungana Hospital *J Rural Trop Pub Health* 2011, 10: 80 - 86 323
- [318] Stride P. Zeehan Hospital, Zeehan, Tasmania. The First Forty Years, During The Mining Boom 1894-1934 The Curious Case of the Missing Lead Poisoning. *Amer J Surg Clin Case Rep.* 2021; 3(13): 1-83
- [319] *Case Rep.* 2021; 3(13): 1-83
- [320] Stride P. Maytown Hospital. *Clin Surg.* 2020; 5: 2974
- [321] Jones E, Nath N, Stride P, Manuja Premaratne, Darshit Thaker, Ivan Lim Impact of a Dugs and Safety Sub-Committee at a Queensland Hospital *Aust Health Management* 2011, 35, 395–398
- [322] Stride P, Seleem M, Nath N, Horne A, Kapitsalas C. Integration of patient safety systems within the suburbs *Australian Health Review* 2012 doi.org/10.1071/AH11099
- [323] Courier Mail 4/2/2023